

Deliverable D3.1

Report on Discipline Requirements and Needs

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Deliverable Abstract

Report presenting methodology and results from the first EOSC EDEN data collection within WP3, aimed at describing discipline and data-type specific requirements. Data are collected among the seven early-adopter disciplines in the project. Recommendations, based on observed commonalities and needs, are structured around the Re-use Fitness model.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
CERN	Organisation européenne pour la recherche nucléaire (European Organization for Nuclear Research)
CSC	CSC - Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus (IT Centre for Science)
DKRZ	Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (German Climate Computing Centre)
DOQ	Digital object quality
KNAW	Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen (Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences)
LTDP	Long-term digital preservation
PMT	Premotec GmbH
PMT (PL)	Premotec Poland SP. Z O.O.
SIB	SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
SURF	SURF BV
TIB	Technische Informationsbibliothek (German National Library of Science and Technology)
UBREMEN	Universität Bremen (University of Bremen)
UESSEX-UKDA	University of Essex; UK Data Archive
UiT	Universitetet i Tromsø - Norges arktiske universitet (UiT The Arctic University of Norway)

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Main Objectives of Task 3.1	4
1.2	Goal of Deliverable 3.1	4
1.3	Organisation of Deliverable 3.1	6
2	Methodology.....	6
2.1	Desk-Based Mapping	7
2.1.1	Spreadsheet Build-Up	8
2.1.2	Data Collection and Synthesis	9
2.2	Stand-Alone Interviews	9
2.2.1	Interview Guide	9
2.2.2	Data Collection and Synthesis	10
2.2.3	Management of Interview Data: Ethical and Legal Considerations.....	11
2.3	Survey.....	12
2.3.1	Context for Development of Discipline-Specific Survey Questions	12
2.3.2	Discipline-Specific Survey Question Section.....	13
3	Results	16
3.1	Desk-Based Mapping	17
3.1.1	Contextual Data Quality.....	17
3.1.2	Technical Data Quality.....	18
3.1.3	Metadata Quality.....	19
3.1.4	Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities	20
3.1.5	Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs.....	22
3.2	Stand-Alone Interviews	22
3.2.1	Contextual Data Quality.....	22
3.2.2	Technical Data Quality.....	23
3.2.3	Metadata Quality.....	23
3.2.4	Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities	24
3.2.5	Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs.....	25
4	Discussion	25
4.1	A Heterogeneous Information Landscape.....	26
4.2	Commonalities and Specificities in Existing Requirements	27
4.3	Emerging Needs in Discipline-Specific Repositories and Communities.....	28
4.3.1	Contextual Data Quality.....	28
4.3.2	Technical Data Quality.....	29

4.3.3	Metadata Quality.....	30
4.3.4	Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities	30
4.3.5	Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs.....	31
4.4	T3.1 Methodology: Perspectives.....	32
5	Summary.....	32
6	References.....	33
7	Appendix.....	35

List of Tables

Table 1	– Question on discipline(s) covered	13
Table 2	– Question on metadata standards	14
Table 3	– Question on file formats.....	14
Table 4	– Question on sensitive data.....	15
Table 5	– Question on needs in community.....	15
Table 6	– Question on potential factors reducing future FAIRness	16
Table 7	– Open end question.....	16

List of Figures

Figure 1	– Data Quality Aspects (taken from Peng et al., 2022, p. 3)	2
Figure 2	– The Re-use Fitness model.....	3
Figure 3	– The workflow in Task 3.1	3

Executive Summary

This report, Deliverable D3.1: “Report on Discipline Requirements and Needs”, is part of the EU-funded project EOSC EDEN, which aims to develop a robust framework for the long-term preservation and reuse of digital research data.¹ The project addresses critical challenges in ensuring that data across diverse scientific disciplines remain accessible, reliable, and reusable over time. This deliverable focuses on identifying discipline-specific requirements, gaps, and emerging needs related to long-term digital preservation (LTDP) and digital object quality (DOQ). The findings will guide the development of frameworks and tools to support researchers, repositories, and other stakeholders working on projects involving research data and other digital objects.

The report is based on a combination of desk-based research of documented repository practices, interviews with researchers and repository managers, and contributions to a survey targeting digital preservation professionals. These methods are used to gather initial insights from seven early-adopter disciplines: Climate Simulations, Earth & Environmental Sciences, Food Sciences, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, Linguistics, and Social Sciences. The analysis is structured around the Re-use Fitness model, which evaluates LTDP and DOQ practices through five key components: contextual data quality, technical data quality, metadata quality, trustworthy digital archive capabilities, and preservation objectives/designated community needs.

Throughout this work, it has become clear that the targeted information landscape is highly heterogeneous. Despite this, there are similarities across disciplines with respect to robust LTDP and DOQ practises (e.g. the preference for open and standardized file formats, widespread use of specialized curators, as well as the use of persistent identifiers), but importantly, all disciplines reveal common challenges. These challenges include the need for standardized documentation and metadata practices, better management of sensitive data, and improved support for open and interoperable file formats. Many repositories lack formal policies for data retention, backups, and exit strategies, which are critical for ensuring LTDP. Additionally, researchers often face difficulties in navigating repository requirements, while repositories struggle with limited resources and funding for sustainable operations.

The report highlights the importance of fostering stronger collaboration between researchers and repositories, improving training and guidance on data management, and developing tools to automate and streamline processes like metadata annotation and file format migration. It also emphasizes the need for repositories to adopt clear policies for data governance, including compliance with ethical and legal standards such as GDPR and the CARE principles for Indigenous data.

The findings underscore the urgency of addressing these challenges to ensure that research data remains accessible and reusable for future generations. Recommendations include creating standardized tools for documentation, enhancing repository certification awareness, and establishing robust financial and operational strategies for repositories.

This deliverable provides a foundation for future work within the EOSC EDEN project, informing the development of practical solutions that will benefit researchers, repositories, and broader scientific communities. By addressing the identified gaps and needs, the project aims to strengthen Europe’s capacity for sustainable and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data stewardsh

¹ The executive summary is a revised output from using the ChatUiT (chat.uit.no) applying the GPT-4o model on the fully amended content of this report.

1 Introduction

The central topic of the EOSC EDEN project is long-term digital preservation of data and other digital objects.² This topic presently receives much attention because of associated costs and physical limitations on storage and service capacity, but also because of unevenly distributed awareness and implementation of preservation practices and standards across scientific disciplines. The EOSC EDEN project has set out to meet these challenges by:

- developing and establishing a framework to identify what data are candidates to long-term digital preservation based on use, benefit, and quality;
- developing a model for re-appraisal points along data lifecycle and test usability;
- identifying practices to support the creation of curation, long-term digital preservation, and access strategies in Europe.

Further, user-centric tools, services and standards will be developed inside the project, which over time will support the establishment of a European distributed infrastructure for long-term digital preservation, curation, and access in Europe.

Essential voices in this endeavour are the disciplinary specialists, one of the main target end-user groups and beneficiaries of the project outcomes. The disciplinary specialists, who possess deep, specialized knowledge within the domain, serve in a wide range of roles, e.g. as researchers, scientific supervisors, data stewards, repository personnel, and management. In addition to having acquired extensive knowledge on theoretical and empirical topics in the field, researchers and academic leaders today are expected to have gained experience and expertise with recommended practices in research data management, in particular mastering articulation of the FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016) and CARE (Carroll et al., 2020) principles in their own research projects or programmes. As for data stewards and repository personnel, not only FAIR and CARE, but also the TRUST principles (Lin et al., 2020) are of importance when developing strategies, roadmaps, and guidelines. To complete the landscape of guiding principles with which repositories should confer, FAIR+Time (L'Hours et al., 2022) adds the temporal dimension to the FAIRness of data and other digital objects and addresses the importance of strategies for planning and reassessing data FAIRness over time.

The more knowledge production relies on large amounts and heterogenous types of data, the more crucial it becomes to ensure that data quality adheres to high standards; and also, more concretely, that the data meet the relevant requirements for reuse. EOSC EDEN aims to develop and establish a framework to support scholars and other personnel involved in management of research data and other digital objects. In this regard, one important tool is effective guidelines for data quality management throughout the lifecycle. By data quality management we mean the ability to provide transparent information necessary to understand the data, ensuring that the data are reliable (e.g., accurate, complete, consistent), and ensuring that the data align with the usage scenario and purpose for which they were collected and preserved.

Data quality management can be described as involving four sub-processes: quality planning, quality control, quality assurance and improving data quality – in an iterative cycle (International Organization for Standardization, 2016; see also Lacagnina et al., 2023). Quality aspects will similarly have to be managed (as well as planned, controlled, assured and improved) within all stages of the lifecycle of digital objects, and necessarily involve the contribution of different roles and stakeholders. Figure 1, published in Peng et al. (2022,

² Parts of Section 1 are recycled from the EOSC EDEN Grant Agreement (2024), in accordance with the guidance provided by the Text Recycling Research Project (Hall et al., 2021).

p. 3), helps stakeholders realise their contribution to data quality aspects. Figure 1 details four main quality aspects, each referring to three key stages in the research process, and further details some quality attributes associated with the main quality aspects.

Figure 1– Data Quality Aspects (taken from Peng et al., 2022, p. 3)

Another essential tool in the development of the EOSC EDEN framework for identification of candidates to long-term digital preservation is the Re-use Fitness model (Fig. 2), a core component of the project grant agreement. The purpose of this model is to serve as a frame for assessing aspects that are important during evaluation of a repository’s strategies for identifying, selecting, and (re)appraising digital objects for long-term digital preservation.

The model approaches the quality aspects in Peng et al. (2022) from a slightly different angle, building on three pillars for data quality, i.e. *Contextual Data Quality*, *Technical Data Quality* and *Metadata Quality*. These three pillars again meet two horizontal dimensions, i.e. *Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs* and *Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities*.

Figure 2 – The Re-use Fitness model

The Re-use Fitness model forms the basis for data collection in EOSC EDEN Work Package 3³ – the WP responsible for this deliverable, whose main role is to provide the project with discipline, cross-discipline, and data-type specific needs and requirements. Adherence to the Re-use Fitness model will ensure interoperability of outputs across the EOSC EDEN Work Packages 1, 2 and 3, which are in close collaboration, as shown in Figure 3 where the role of Task 3.1 is highlighted.

Figure 3 – The workflow in Task 3.1

³ WP3: Discipline-specific requirements, validation and future use

1.1 Main Objectives of Task 3.1

The ever-evolving digital research landscape, combined with the lack of cross-disciplinary integration of data quality standards and routines for long-term digital preservation, may lead to disparities in data quality within and across disciplines. These factors further run the risk of obscuring how to best approach long-term preservation of FAIR, high-quality data to benefit transparency, openness and sharing of knowledge inside and across research communities. The role of Task 3.1 is to bring the expert opinions of disciplinary specialists into the discussion.

A first main objective of Task 3.1 (Months 1–32; “M” is hereafter used to abbreviate working Month) is to map discipline-specific, cross-disciplinary, and digital object type-specific requirements and needs related to long-term digital preservation and digital object quality. A second main objective, as illustrated in Figure 3, is to iteratively feed WP1⁴ and WP2⁵ with synthesised insights and specific case examples derived from this analysis. The two main objectives are achieved by means of three different data collection methods, and what can be described as method triangulation. The motivation for this combined use of methods is to achieve a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the landscape than is possible by using one method alone. Even more important in this context is the possible refinement of methods over time, made possible by iterative reporting via the present deliverable (M6) and two milestones (M18 and M28).

The partners involved in Task 3.1 represent seven disciplines that function as early adopters in the EOSC EDEN project, i.e. Climate Simulations (DKRZ), Earth & Environmental Sciences (UBREMEN), Food Sciences (PMT), High-Energy Physics (CERN), Life Sciences & Bioinformatics (SIB), Linguistics (UiT), and Social Sciences (KNAW, UESSEX-UKDA). These partners are responsible in the project for identifying and analysing the diverse needs and challenges of the given disciplines, and for transforming these into tangible requirements and feedback to work packages in charge of developing the framework and model (WP1) and the tools (WP2). The two other partners involved in Task 3.1, SURF and TIB, bring in expertise on provision of digital preservation tools and services, and are key contributors to ensuring that observations are handed over to WP1 and WP2 as insightful and ready-to-use material.

1.2 Goal of Deliverable 3.1

The first six months of the EOSC EDEN project, leading up to this deliverable, can be characterised as an initial learning phase, during which the Task 3.1 members have reflected on, discussed, and tested ways of approaching the action at hand. Key discussion points have been the purpose(s) of the task, topical aspects to focus on during data collection, target groups, interactions with other WPs, objective of the first deliverable, and internal project timelines.

The EOSC EDEN grant agreement states that main target groups in Task 3.1 (henceforth T3.1) will include networks, projects, and other entities that manage research data and other digital objects⁶ within and across disciplines, and which primarily operate at a national, regional, or global level.⁷ The grant agreement further

⁴ WP1: *Data and process framework for long-term digital preservation*

⁵ WP2: *Long-term access and preservation services & tools*

⁶ Though it is acknowledged that data created and collected by and of relevance to researchers is important, the scope of the digital objects in the project is broader. This can include any identified digital entity consisting of “data” and/or “metadata” in the broadest sense. This includes, but is not limited to software, code, workflows, ontologies, semantic artefacts, standards, schemas, and workflows. Some digital objects are digital metadata records that describe physical entities, including but not limited to, people, scientific instruments, works of art, and blood samples.

⁷ Examples mentioned in the proposal are groups under the [RDA for Disciplines, GO FAIR Implementation Networks](#), and entities within [ESFRI/ERICs](#). Other examples mentioned are cross-domain-oriented and

states that more discipline-specific groups will be included to test and ensure the practical and feasible implementation of the framework and tools developed during the project.⁸

In this first, exploratory phase of T3.1, our goal has been two-fold: firstly, to develop and test our methodology and secondly, to assemble an initial overview of data quality assurance and long-term digital preservation practices within and across the above-mentioned seven disciplines. With these goals in mind, we decided early on to approach a rich variety of stakeholders during the first round of data collection. This decision has necessarily put some limits on the extent of representativeness and details in the final data that underpin this report. Future data collections within T3.1 aim to be more narrow and in-depth, with focus on specific aspects identified in collaboration with WP1 and WP2.

The current deliverable has multiple purposes and functions inside the EOSC EDEN project. It serves as:

- **input to WP1, Y1:** The discipline-specific survey question section (cf. Section 2.3) is delivered to T1.1⁹ and integrated into the “EOSC-EDEN survey on identification, appraisal and selection of digital data for long-term digital preservation”. Results will be reported in D1.1¹⁰ (M12). Also relevant to mention, the desk-based mapping (cf. Section 2.1) in its current state offers a starting point for fine-tuning the research on file formats used within the disciplines. Preservation metrics related to file format will receive strong focus from T1.2¹¹ in Y2 and Y3 of the project, and ongoing conversations already indicate how T3.1 may proceed to support T1.2 in this action.
- **input to WP2, Y1:** In the current document, we report on discipline-specific requirements gathered through multiple lines of investigation. These requirements will need to be translated into technical specifications using a custom platform (Jira) which is implemented and maintained by T2.1¹². This deliverable will act as guidance on the translation of requirements into technical specifications for the selection and/or development of preservation tools and services.
- **input to WP3 T3.1, Y2:** In accordance with the EOSC EDEN grant agreement, T3.1 will iteratively feed WP1 and WP2 with synthesised insights and specific case examples from the disciplines. This implies additional data collections. The work carried out in connection with the present deliverable provides a substantial basis for future refinement of the selected methods.
- **input to WP3 T3.2, Y1:** T3.2¹³ is defining user-journey maps to describe the requirements reported in this deliverable in terms of workflows and practical scenarios. As such, the material reported here is directly connected to the work of T3.2, especially in the months leading up to Milestone 3.1 (M10). Additionally, T3.2 must define the criteria for the assessment of the implementation of requirements, user-journeys, and specifications. The information contained in this deliverable will allow us to define this pilot methodology in a discipline-informed way.
- **input to WP4, Y1:** T4.2¹⁴ is creating an expert curation network (discipline-oriented) that will enhance and facilitate the curation process and digital preservation actions to ensure data remain accessible as technology changes. Currently, there is considerable variation across disciplines and data types

generalist efforts such as the [Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework \(CDIF\)](#), the [DDI Cross-Domain Integration \(DDI-CDI\)](#), the [W3C Data on the Web Best Practices group](#), and [Science Clusters/OSCARS](#).

⁸ The main focus inside T3.1 is to work with the seven early-adopter disciplines, but when considered useful for the action at hand, additional discipline-specific groups will be invited to contribute via communication channels identified in collaboration with WP4.

⁹ T1.1: *Collection, comparison and evaluation of existing frameworks, guidelines and practices for identification, selection & appraisal of data for long-term preservation.*

¹⁰ D1.1: *Overview of identification, selection and appraisal practices for data long-term preservation*

¹¹ T1.2: *Definition of requirements in long-term preservation processes for re-use fitness of information objects*

¹² T2.1: *Definition systems requirements and specifications*

¹³ T3.2: *Pilot methodology and validation*

¹⁴ T4.2: *Creating an expert curation network*

when it comes to available network support and how focused these collaborations are on long-term digital preservation and data quality aspects. This report will serve as valuable input to the discussions in the first network workshop scheduled for October 2025, whose goal is to define a strategy and roadmap for the network.

- **input to WP5, Y1:** The stand-alone interviews (cf. Section 2.2) have served as testing grounds for handling data containing person-identifying information inside the EOSC EDEN consortium. T5.1¹⁵ is responsible for the overall data management plan of the project, and may benefit from this deliverable when revisiting the plan. Also, information about the workflow in the active phase (from collection to analysis) with several international partners involved in all stages, will be valuable for other EOSC EDEN actions using the same data collection methodology.

In addition to its value to the EOSC EDEN project, this deliverable and the associated data will be of use to the EOSC FIDELIS project; in particular the FIDELIS T5.2¹⁶ landscape analysis due in M10.

1.3 Organisation of Deliverable 3.1

This report is organised into three main parts. Section 2 introduces and discusses the methodology selected for the three T3.1-related data collections carried out in Year 1 of the project, i.e. desk-based mapping, semi-structured interviews, and survey questions. Section 3 details the results extracted from the desk-based mapping and the interviews, respectively, organised by the five components in the Re-use Fitness model. Section 4 analyses commonalities and specificities observed across disciplines, with a particular focus on the needs that have been identified.

The data collected during the desk-based mapping and the interviews are presented in a synthesised format in Zenodo (see Appendix). The raw data for the desk-based mapping, in their current state, are also made publicly available, while the transcriptions and raw mapping data for the interviews will remain available for project-internal use only. The full, T3.1-related data collections will be enhanced over the years to come via other EOSC EDEN actions, and will be evaluated for publication upon completion of the project in 2027.

2 Methodology

The EOSC EDEN grant agreement states that T3.1 will employ three approaches to identify existing requirements, gaps, and needs related to long-term digital preservation and digital object quality (henceforth LTDP and DOQ, respectively):

- Perform a desk-based mapping of existing requirements based on standards, recommendations, community norms and practices in addition to identifying knowledge gaps, challenges, barriers and future needs;
- Create survey question content to be included in the main requirements collection run by WP1, addressing clarification of issues in existing requirements and needs as well as addressing gaps and lacks from the discipline perspective;
- Conduct semi-structured interviews as a stand-alone tool and to follow up survey responses, as needed, to collect user stories and community norms and expectations focusing on disciplinary, cross-disciplinary and data type-related requirements and needs.

The work in T3.1 will address the whole data stewardship lifecycle, including deposit criteria, initial curation, technical watch, community watch, appraisal and reappraisal and quality metrics, examined in terms of technical compliance, scientific quality, feasibility, and scalability. The balance of machine-actionability vs.

¹⁵ T5.1: *Project coordination, administrative and financial management and internal communication*

¹⁶ T5.2: *Preparing for federation*

human mediated actions will be considered, as well as the relation between discipline-agnostic and discipline-specific requirements.

As introduced in Section 1, the work in T3.1 must be clearly connected and aligned with the work in WP1 and WP2. In this initial phase of the project, we have decided on an inclusive approach in order to capture a wide range of nuances related to the data stewardship lifecycle. In practice, this has resulted in a desk-based mapping methodology open to a rich variety of documents, an interview methodology targeting different stakeholders, and a survey methodology allowing respondents to detail their answers either via check boxes or via open text fields. A continuous dialogue with the other work packages has helped us shape the data collection and analysis in the planned direction, but we have still approached the task with methodological openness in order to not miss useful aspects. One consequence is that this approach results in a broad, yet potentially fragmented picture of the information landscape. This means that we currently cannot provide a comprehensive list of requirements, needs and gaps that fully cover a given discipline, and the conclusions that we draw can be improved upon in the future. Conversely, the methodological approach selected provides the EOSC EDEN consortium with a set of emerging trends and a foundation upon which we can construct more focused and systematic data collections in later iterations.

As indicated, the data collections carried out in connection with this deliverable relate to aspects of the whole data stewardship lifecycle. Note however that some framing perspectives are not addressed in this first iteration of data collection:

- **Feasibility:** How feasible it will be for communities to implement the outputs of EDEN will necessarily be examined once the framework and tools from WP1 and WP2 are ready to be tested.
- **Scalability:** Whether the outputs allow communities to start small and scale up gradually is another aspect that needs to await testable outputs from WP1 and WP2.
- **Machine-actionability vs. human mediated actions:** The potential for automation and efficient technical processes, also relevant for feasibility and scalability, will be addressed when tool development in WP2 has progressed.

In what follows, we present in detail the three methods employed; in Section 2.1 the desk-based mapping, in Section 2.2 the semi-structured interviews, and in Section 2.3 the survey.

2.1 Desk-Based Mapping

Assessing the discipline-specific landscape, with respect to LTDP and guarantees for DOQ, is a necessary step so that future adopters can effectively use the EOSC EDEN project outcomes. The first method involves a detailed examination of the documentation that is freely available online for the repositories and communities associated with the seven early-adopter disciplines (cf. Section 1.1).

During this mapping exercise, relevant information surrounding LTDP and DOQ is targeted and mapped according to project-relevant themes. The overall mapping involves:

1. Identification of appropriate discipline-related repositories and communities;
2. Discovery of relevant documentation for LTDP and DOQ, which could include formally published documents, preprints, or online protocols or routines that accompany a repository, as well as policy and strategy documents relating to the respective community; and
3. Harvesting and synthesis of relevant information from the aforementioned documents into predefined categories in a working spreadsheet document.

The desk-based mapping will be a representation of not only what practices are currently adopted across the disciplines, but also what information is robustly documented in these repositories. The documents examined

are written for diverse motives and purposes and therefore do not always represent a complete picture of community needs or implementations within repositories. As a whole, however, they are very suitable for depicting the landscape in question.

2.1.1 Spreadsheet Build-Up

The first step in gathering the detailed information regarding discipline-specific requirements is to ensure that data collection proceeds in an organized and traceable manner. References to documents that were candidates for review were added to the joint FIDELIS and EOSC EDEN Zotero group library¹⁷. The T3.1 Desk-based Mapping tabular document¹⁸ was created to record and organize all information sources used in the forthcoming mapping exercise. The initial T3.1_DBM_Documents_V1 worksheet was created, where individual identifiers (with the format IDXX) were assigned to each document related to a distinct repository or community from which information was gathered and distilled. These identifiers will be used to cross-link the (requirement) fields in the main data gathering worksheet. Each individual document entry also includes the name of the Repository/Community, an URL, identifying information for any documentation accompanying the repository (identified with metadata such as PID, title, date), plus a record of who is responsible for information gathering for the given Repository/Community. Where appropriate, the EOSC EDEN Zotero links were also added.

To construct the main data gathering worksheet, documents related to well-known generalist and discipline-specific repositories were reviewed. These documents proved to be heterogeneous in terms of source, purpose, content, and structure, and furthermore their content often reflected the natural cycle of research data management used by data stewards, that flows from project planning, active data collection, data processing, and finally data publishing, as well as the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016). These factors presented challenges in our effort to standardise the gathering and structuring of information that concentrated on LTDP and DOQ. To ensure a clear and standardized reporting method where the sourced information is understandable from a discipline-specific user perspective – while simultaneously being interoperable with relevant tasks in WP1 and WP2 – the main data gathering worksheet, T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1, was created and structured around the Re-use Fitness model (Fig. 2) and the most relevant elements of the Curation Lifecycle Model (Digital Curation Centre, 2004-2024). In collaboration with WP1, the key principles of repository data preservation and digital object quality were aligned to the five components of the Re-use Fitness model (Fig. 2). Subcategories related to the repository-specific criteria were mapped beneath each of these five overarching categories. For example, the pillar *Metadata Quality* would include individual data entries that describe if the repository had criteria to maintain robust and interoperable metadata, which included items that ranged from metadata standards or controlled vocabularies, to identifying the granularity of PIDs assigned to digital object for preservation. The structure and content of the T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1 worksheet was given to project partners in WP1 and WP3 to review for completeness and comments. Edits were made to achieve both intra-project interoperability and accommodating language used within the discipline repository environment.

In addition, the seven disciplines were added to the worksheet, and when possible, classified according to the OECD Fields of Research and Development (FORD) level 1 and level 2 for additional granularity (OECD, 2015).¹⁹

¹⁷ https://www.zotero.org/groups/5836663/fidelis_and_eosc_eden/library

¹⁸ This document is for internal use only. All other DBM-related documents can be accessed via the Appendix.

¹⁹ Note that the FORD categories were not applicable for Food Sciences because this discipline is a multidisciplinary research area that incorporates a number of disciplines within the FORD classification. Multidisciplinary research areas are all compiled of a selection of different disciplines. This necessarily means that no classification of research disciplines will accurately represent each and every particular combination.

Upon completion of the main worksheet structure, the T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1 worksheet was disseminated to the T3.1 group for information gathering.

2.1.2 Data Collection and Synthesis

The sourced information was collected and entered into the worksheet T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1 in the appropriate categories by project partners from the seven disciplines. Following discipline classification, the partners entered as much information as available in the resources into the spreadsheet. The information entered is purely textual and also diverse, because many subcategories identified during 2.1.1 do not permit prescribed formats due to the heterogeneous nature of documents available across repositories and communities. Where possible, standard reporting conventions were used, for example, using the CoreTrustSeal's curation level system (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2024) when assessing the level of curation under the category *Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs*.

Upon completion of data collection into the T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1 worksheet, the data was synthesized to identify established requirements and observable gaps and needs for the five main categories, within each of the seven disciplines. This was completed in a third spreadsheet T3.1_DBM_Synthesized_Requirements_V1, and the data entry was structured such that all subcategories were merged into two cells: *Existing Requirements* and *Future Needs/Knowledge Gaps*. For example, under the main category *Metadata Quality*, all data from subcategories *Metadata Standard*, *Controlled Vocabulary*, *License*, *PID*, *PID granularity*, *Access ± Embargo ± Restrictions*, and *Technical and Administrative Metadata in addition to Description* would be analyzed together. A lack of information (e.g. blank cell) in the T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1 worksheet was interpreted as no information available in the supporting documents listed in T3.1_DBM_Documents_V1.

The goal of the data synthesis was to (1) identify what LTDP and DOQ information is already documented and in practice within a community, which lead naturally to (2) identifying the gaps and needs across the disciplines. In T3.1_DBM_Synthesized_Requirements_V1, the information identified in (1) was summarized in the *Existing Requirements* column, and that for (2) was described in the *Future Needs/Knowledge Gaps* column. During the synthesis, it was prudent to quantify the number of entries per discipline to avoid biased results from overrepresented disciplines. Furthermore, it was also prudent to be aware that some disciplines by their very nature may not have accounted for some areas of LTDP and DOQ. As a concrete example, a physical science (excluded from the Life Sciences) such as High-Energy Physics would have no information for GDPR due to the absence of person-identifying data collected within this discipline. During synthesis, it was recognized that WP members may have introduced bias into the data compilation process due to their individual expertise and knowledge of community practices that are specific to the disciplines. This knowledge may extend beyond what is officially recorded and explicitly mentioned within the analysed documents.

2.2 Stand-Alone Interviews

The stand-alone interviews of T3.1 represent a critical component of WP3's effort to define discipline-specific and cross-disciplinary requirements for LTDP and DOQ. The interviews complement the desk-based mapping and survey (cf. Section 2.3) by providing insights via user-stories towards understanding active LTDP, quality assessment and reappraisal of digital objects across the seven early-adopter disciplines (cf. Section 1.1).

2.2.1 Interview Guide

The interview guide (see Appendix) was developed jointly by the T3.1 members as a guide to the interviewer when collecting the desired qualitative insights. The guide ensures the harmonised gathering of user stories, community norms, and expectations from the two primary stakeholder groups – researchers and repository managers. The guide was structured with flexibility in mind while maintaining consistency across interviews. Questions were structured thematically around the data lifecycle, touching upon deposit criteria, curation,

technical watch, community watch, appraisal, reappraisal, quality metrics, technical compliance (e.g., metadata, file formats, ontologies), and scientific quality. Separate sets of questions were developed for researchers and repository managers to address their unique perspectives.

2.2.1.1 Researcher-Oriented Set of Questions

The researcher-oriented questions were designed to explore the viewpoints and incentives of persons frequently handling research data, associated with career stages R2 to R4 (European Commission, 2011). The interviews also focused on needs and challenges in preserving research data in the involved disciplines. Key focus areas in the interview guide were:

- Context and practices for research data (research topics, practices relating to data types, data discovery, data collection, processing, and archiving).
- Incentives and motivations to deposit data and if these are influenced by mandatory practices via funders, institutions or other third parties, and if there are benefits for the researcher in their community and society.
- Researchers' decision-making process for file formats and metadata selection for LTDP and their expectations regarding future availability and replaceability of their data.
- Researcher expectations for interacting and communicating with repositories (and experiences when depositing data, reusing data, and the information and services provided to users).
- Researcher experiences with reusing data and the evaluation of repositories, including their data in terms of quality and trustworthiness (reflecting also on situations when data is reused and the perception of their respective level of FAIRness).
- Researcher challenges and needs when managing and preserving data, including discipline-specific challenges, weaknesses or gaps in FAIRness of research data and how these can be improved.

2.2.1.2 Repository Manager-Oriented Set of Questions

A specific set of questions were designed for repository managers and aimed to understand policies, practices, and challenges that repositories are facing in the archiving of digital objects. Key focus areas in the interview guide were:

- Content specialization of repositories with data types accepted for digital preservation, and the user groups expected to interact with the repository.
- Which LTDP policies and guidelines drive the repository, and what stages and parts of the data cycle (cf. e.g. Digital Curation Centre, 2004-2024) are considered for archiving (raw data, processed data, metadata, etc.).
- Challenges faced by the repository service regarding the maintenance of data quality and how the service ensures quality, integrity, access, and security as a whole.
- The repository's approach to appraisal and reappraisal practices of stored digital objects over time and how decisions, e.g. considering scientific quality, are taken in these approaches.
- The repository's communication with its user base (how the user needs are being identified, communicated, and implemented, and how evolving technological demands, advances, and formats are dealt with by the repository).
- The governance and sustainability of a given repository, focusing on challenges to achieving sustainability over time and if a succession or exit plan is formally established in case of funding shortages or expiration.

2.2.2 Data Collection and Synthesis

Interview participants were identified through networks of T3.1 members, ensuring representation from both researchers and repository managers within each early-adopter discipline. A minimum of one researcher and

one repository manager per discipline was targeted, with additional participants included where feasible to capture diversity within disciplines. Eighteen interviews, (with one additional repository manager and researcher in High-energy Physics and Life Sciences & Bioinformatics respectively and an extra set for Linguistics) were carried out in person or through conference tools (like Zoom or MS Teams), by members in T3.1 from the same discipline as the interviewee. Interviews were aimed at lasting a maximum of 1 hour. A set of rule conventions were made for the quality assessment of audio transcripts including anonymisation and procedures for file naming.²⁰

Once the interview recordings were completed, they were uploaded by the interviewer to a task-shared environment in UiT SharePoint which is approved for data containing person-identifying information. The interview files (.m4a format) were converted using the VLC media player to .mp3 format before being transcribed with the UiT service Klartekst²¹. Transcripts were manually inspected for inconsistencies like hallucinations, repeated sentences, and misspellings. Unrecognizable words and untranscribable parts of the recordings were marked and codes applied according to the agreed coding convention. Both .mp3 files and cleaned transcripts were uploaded to the task's shared environment.

The interview transcripts were further analysed by T3.1 members who manually populated statements by the interviewees into a T3.1 Interview tabular document²², labeled T3.1_Interviews_Requirements_V1, which is an expanded version of T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1. The sheet followed the DBM design as described in Section 2.1.1 with an expansion of the four additional subcategories including comments:

- *Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities; Governance, Comments*
- *Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs; Program-Related Tools/Tech Watch, Motivation and Attitudes, Training and Dialogue with Repository, Comments*
- *Technical Data Quality; Comments*
- *Metadata quality; Comments*
- *Contextual data quality; Comments*

Transcribed statements by researchers and repository managers were manually interpreted and summarised into each of the 39 categories.

A synthesis exercise advanced the analysis by creating a consensus of the five main components of the Re-use Fitness model (Fig. 2) into *Existing Requirements/Practices* and the perceived *Future Needs/Knowledge Gaps*, see T3.1_Interviews_Synthesized_Requirements_V1 (link in Appendix). T3.1 members manually performed the synthesis exercise in a discipline-oriented fashion, extracting information either directly derived from the interviews or indirectly from the context via interpretation.

2.2.3 Management of Interview Data: Ethical and Legal Considerations

In connection with the collection of interview data, the project has captured a limited amount of personal information. These are processed confidentially in accordance with current legislation and guidelines for data

²⁰ See details on management of interview data including overview of respondents in Appendix.

²¹ "Klartekst is a transcription service based on artificial intelligence that uses a language model called Whisper to perform transcription. Whisper is an advanced, neural network-based transcription model developed by OpenAI. It is designed to transcribe speech to text with high accuracy, even under challenging conditions such as background noise or dialects. In the Klartekst service, users can upload audio files, which the Whisper model will analyze and convert into written text. [...] Klartekst is approved for green, yellow, and red data." (taken from UiT The Arctic University of Norway, n.d., and automatically translated using Microsoft Copilot).

²² This document is for project-internal use only given the potential person-identifying information extracted via the statements.

management at the data controlling institutions (UiT The Arctic University of Norway and CSC – IT Center for Science). Prior to data collection, legal approval was granted by Sikt – Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (project reference number 208897).

All participants were informed about the purpose of the study and signed a consent form that includes information about future use and dissemination of content.

The interviews generated one sound file and one transcription file per respondent. Directly identifiable information, i.e. name and institution, has been replaced with codes during verification of transcriptions. Indirectly identifiable information such as geographical location and defining characteristics of research area and/or repository data holdings, will be evaluated prior to deletion of the scrambling key and the sound files, no later than in year 3 of the project. The final transcriptions will be archived with the necessary access level.

The future steps of data management will proceed in accordance with the EOSC EDEN data management plan (cf. D5.2) and the T3.1-internal data management plan residing on FAIR Wizard Norway.

2.3 Survey

Being responsible for the discipline-specific dimension of the EOSC EDEN project, T3.1 has contributed a set of questions to the first EOSC EDEN survey²³, developed by T1.1 in WP1 and entitled “EOSC-EDEN survey on identification, appraisal and selection of digital data for long-term digital preservation”. The survey, conducted in the period May-June 2025 and to be reported in D1.1, is part of WP1’s landscape analysis and focuses on *Contextual Data Quality*, one of the three pillars of the Re-use Fitness model (see Fig. 2). It is targeted at repository personnel. The survey is designed to understand how digital preservation professionals work within their repositories, to learn about existing frameworks, guidelines and practices for identification, selection and (re-)appraisal of data for LTDP, and what “long-term” means in different organisational and professional settings.

2.3.1 Context for Development of Discipline-Specific Survey Questions

T3.1 created a set of questions to contribute to the clarification of discipline-specific requirements for repositories regarding LTDP, and moreover to collect information about relevant gaps and needs from the discipline-level perspective. Two impactful practical aspects are worth mentioning: 1) The T3.1 survey input had to be completed at an early stage due to the external deadline from WP1 for survey publication, and 2) WP1 required that we limit the T3.1 survey input to one page in the survey tool (ca. 7 questions) to keep the survey concise and user-friendly.

To develop the list of discipline-specific questions, representatives from the seven early-adopter disciplines proposed questions from their disciplinary point of view. These were then intensively discussed during the writing process, with regard to content, phrasing and question type. The final selection of questions was subsequently delivered to and discussed in close collaboration with T1.1 to make sure they fit well into the survey, both on the formal level (not too many questions, coherent LTDP vocabulary, avoidance of open questions to facilitate subsequent data analysis) and on the content level (avoidance of content duplications, coherent survey structure). Any other questions that were considered important, but not fitting in the survey requirements, were integrated into the stand-alone interviews, as these permitted a more flexible procedure and qualitative analysis.

²³ See link to survey questions in Appendix.

2.3.2 Discipline-Specific Survey Question Section

This subsection details the discipline-specific questions and their answer options. Relevant T3.1-internal discussions are reported for the various questions, as these present the arguments for selecting questions, answer options, and phrasing.

Table 1 – Question on discipline(s) covered

Question	Answer Options
Digital objects of which research discipline(s) are stored by your organisation? Please select as many as apply.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Natural sciences ● Engineering and technology ● Medical and health sciences ● Agricultural and veterinary sciences ● Social sciences ● Humanities and the arts ● Generic / no discipline speciality ● We have a specific interdisciplinary scope. <p>= FORD Classification (OECD, 2015)²⁴ (subcategories are displayed in the survey once a top category is checked)</p>

One of the earliest and most obvious discussions to be had within T3.1 was the question of which classification of research disciplines to use. Both EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects had to be involved in the discussion to find and possibly agree on a commonly suitable controlled vocabulary to be used throughout the project runtime. The classification to use had to fulfill several requirements to ensure that the results of T3.1 would be comparable to other project outputs as well as further research beyond the project:

- Suitability for both the EOSC EDEN and the FIDELIS project and their respective goals.
- Granularity of research disciplines had to be fine enough and fitting to represent the input and results from the seven EOSC EDEN early-adopter disciplines.
- Sustainability and comparability of the project results and findings meant that a globally applicable discipline classification was advised.

A first idea suggested by the FIDELIS project was to use the controlled vocabulary from the re3data “Metadata Schema for the Description of Research Data Repositories” (Strecker et al., 2023), as re3data serves as a widely used registry for repositories in Europe. Re3data’s classification of research disciplines is based on the DFG’s (German Research Foundation) “Classification of Scientific Disciplines, Research Areas, Review Boards and Subject Areas” (2021). This classification offers a fine discipline granularity that also captured the EOSC EDEN early-adopter disciplines well. However, as it was developed by the German Research Foundation, the classification was designed from a national and eurocentric point of view as a default perspective (e.g. “104 Linguistics → 10401 General and Applied Linguistics, 10403 Typology, Non-European Languages, Historical Linguistics”), fit for its purpose for classifying research objects from a national perspective. When used in a global context, however, this German and eurocentric perspective would be discriminatory against non-European users.

Instead, the OECD Fields of Research and Development (FORD) classification (OECD, 2015) was chosen. This classification of research fields is less granular, e.g. its level 2 (finest granularity) category “1.5 Earth and related environmental sciences”, a subcategory of “Natural sciences”, would capture both early-adopter disciplines Earth & Environmental Sciences and Climate Simulations. However, it was developed from a

²⁴ See Appendix.

globally applicable perspective and thus deemed more suitable for the audience and comparability of the projects' results as a whole.

Table 2– Question on metadata standards

Question	Answer Options
Which descriptive metadata standard(s) is/are commonly used in your organisation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CMDI (Component MetaData Infrastructure) ● CRMtex ● DDI-C Data Documentation Initiative - Codebook ● DDI-L Data Documentation Initiative - Lifecycle ● DDI-CDI (Cross-Domain Integration) ● Dublin Core ● DataCite Metadata Schema ● DCAT ● Darwin Core/EML ● EAD (Encoded Archive Description) ● ENA (European Nucleotide Archive) metadata model/EGA model (life sciences) ● ISO 639-3 (Codes for the representation of names of languages – Part 3: Alpha-3 code for comprehensive coverage of languages) ● ISO19115 (Geographic information – Metadata) ● IMDI (ISLE MetaData Initiative) ● LIFT (Lexington Interchange Format) ● MARC ● MIAME/MINSEQ (life sciences) ● OLAC Metadata ● TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) Guidelines ● TEI/EPIDOC ● UMM (Unified Metadata Model) ● Other (please specify)

This question was designed to learn about metadata standards commonly used in the research disciplines and actually adopted by organisations and repositories in the communities. The descriptive standards in this list resulted from the input of the T3.1 members and thus include the standards used by the EOSC EDEN early-adopter disciplines as well as widely used more general standards. To capture missing standards, there is an “Other (please specify)” option, which opens a free text field when checked. If none of the boxes are checked by the respondents and no “Other” metadata standard is specified, this may be interpreted as a gap or uncertainty in this area of the repository’s guidelines and recommendations.

Table 3 – Question on file formats

Question	Answer Options
Does your organisation recommend (a list of) preferred file formats?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No ● I don't know. <p><u>If yes:</u> Please provide a link to the list where publicly available, or list the preferred formats:</p> <p><u>If no:</u> Please list the most common formats stored in your repository:</p>

This question was designed to inform WP2 in particular about file formats as technical requirements that are commonly recommended within discipline-specific repositories and thus need to be taken into account when developing tools for automated preservation actions. As the list of recommended file formats may be very extensive, we opted for a rather open question with specification options instead of a list of file format options from our respective research disciplines. The “no” and “I don’t know” answer options will also indicate gaps in this area of guidelines and recommendations.

Table 4 – Question on sensitive data

Question	Answer Options
Does your organisation accept sensitive data, or data that requires specific protection?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don’t know <p><u>if yes:</u> Please specify the reason(s) why protection is required by your data objects (multiple answers possible):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection of human rights • Protection of national security • Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study • Protection of legal process and public order • Protection of intellectual property rights • Protection of personal information • Protection of secret and secret Indigenous knowledge • Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species • Other (please specify)

The possible reasons for necessary data protection are manifold and cannot be reduced to privacy issues alone. The different scientific disciplines certainly have different main reasons for protecting their data, which will need to be considered in the discipline-specific guidelines EOSC EDEN aims to develop.

The multiple-choice answer options in case of “yes” were taken from the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021, p. 11, clause 8) for enhanced comparability within and beyond the project. Once one of the answer options is checked, respondents are asked to specify “For each type of sensitivity chosen, please specify the protection measure(s) taken:”, e.g. anonymisation or different storage access levels, in a free text field.

“Other” followed by a free text specification will capture any discipline-specific reasons not represented in the UNESCO list of answers. The “I don’t know” answer option can indicate a gap in the repository’s guidelines and recommendations on this topic.

Table 5 – Question on needs in community

Question	Answer Options
Does your designated community have needs that your organisation does currently not address?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don’t know. <p><u>If yes:</u> Please specify:</p>

This question explicitly asks about perceived community-specific gaps and needs from the repository personnel's view that were not captured by any of the survey questions so far. As these user needs can be manifold and may vary across the scientific disciplines, they can be specified in the free text answer option once “yes” has been checked. While “no” indicates perceived overall satisfaction with the repository services, “I don't know” can indicate a gap in awareness regarding user needs from the repository side. This gap could be addressed by the discipline-specific guidelines to be developed by the project.

Table 6 – Question on potential factors reducing future FAIRness

Question	Answer Options
In your opinion, which factors could reduce the findability, accessibility, interoperability, or reusability over time of digital data objects preserved by your organisation?	free text

In a first version of this question, we phrased it as “Which risks can you already identify that would make your data un-FAIR in 10 years (or more) from now?”. However, after intensive discussion we came to the conclusion that the focus of the former phrasing on FAIR and the timeframe of 10 years was too narrow, as respondents who are not too familiar with the FAIR principles might be confused and skip this question entirely. The goal of this question was to identify what first comes to mind when repository personnel are thinking about the future FAIRness of their digital objects, whether short- or long-term. So the explicit mentioning of “10 years” seemed limiting.

Thus, after discussions with T1.1, the question was rephrased in a more general way. As the factors for reducing data quality over time can be manifold and vary depending on the research discipline, it was decided to not provide a list of pre-formulated answers but to let respondents answer in free text. Admittedly, the answers will be more complicated to systematise, but at the same time these may, in addition to offering insight into what repository managers consider to be noteworthy challenges, help extracting and formulating more systematic questions for other EOSC EDEN tasks. In addition, making all possible options available would require very many boxes, with a remaining uncertainty if the answer options really capture what is conceived as potential challenges for the repositories.

Table 7 – Open end question

Question	Answer Options
Is there anything else you would like to tell us?	free text

This final question serves as a possibility for the respondents to comment on aspects that we might have missed or that could not be covered due to the conciseness of the survey. Any relevant aspects entered for this question can be picked up and discussed during data collections in later iterations.

3 Results

This section presents the results from the desk-based mapping and the stand-alone interviews, respectively.²⁵ The content in Sections 3.1 and 3.2 is organised around the five main components of the Re-use Fitness model (Fig. 2), i.e. *Contextual Data Quality*, *Technical Data Quality*, *Metadata Quality*, *Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities*, and *Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs*.

²⁵ Let us recall that the results from the survey will be reported in D1.1 (due in M12).

Information about where to access details in the results is listed in the Appendix.

3.1 Desk-Based Mapping

As detailed in Section 2.1.2, comprehensive information resulting from the desk-based mapping of discipline-specific repositories and communities were initially collected into the spreadsheet T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1. This information was then condensed in the T3.1_DBM_Synthesized_Requirements_V1 worksheet to provide discipline-specific summaries of documented requirements and also notable gaps and needs. Below, we will report the main results of the desk-based mapping observed across all disciplines, with notable discipline-specific information being identified when pertinent. To refer to specific examples, we will use the identifier in T3.1_DBM_Documents_V1 with the following structure: IDXX. The main existing requirements for each of the five components of the Re-use Fitness model, as well as listing notable gaps will be detailed in the following subsections. Future needs arising from the mapping exercise will be discussed in Section 4.3. Note that for the desk-based mapping exercise, a lack of data (e.g. an empty cell in T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1) will be considered as a gap in requirements. Finally, some disciplines contain entries that are publications or documents that describe data handling, and are not repositories for data deposition, and as such have comparatively less information available for synthesis. Such entries are common for the Food Sciences (e.g. ID40-43; 67) and Life Sciences & Bioinformatics (ID11-13; 15, 19).

3.1.1 Contextual Data Quality

This category includes the following subcategories: *Required Documentation* (e.g. ReadMe files, mandatory metadata), *Data Rights/Consent Held for Publication*, if a *Language* is stipulated, if there are any *GDPR* or *Sensitive Data Evaluations*, and if there are requirements for *Reproduction proof* requirements for data.

3.1.1.1 Required Documentation

Overall, there is moderate information across all disciplines in this category, excluding High-Energy Physics and Linguistics, which have only few data entries in the subcategories. Generally, repositories and communities in all disciplines except Food Sciences require context information typically as part of discipline-specific metadata entries, or a documentation file (e.g. a ReadMe file) to accompany digital objects with further information required on model input data, used software, and methodologies. This is particularly documented for Earth & Environmental Sciences (ID62 & ID64 requiring station and model configuration information) and the Social Sciences (ID47 has explicit documentation requirements), with thorough help documents and quality handbooks available particularly for the Life Sciences repositories.

3.1.1.2 Data Rights/Consent Held for Publication

In contrast, there is very little information concerning *Data Rights/Consent Held for Publication*, with some entries indicating the availability of “Terms of Use”, and “Open Research Data” policies; this lack of information was flagged by one compiler due to a potential misunderstanding by the T3.1 working group of this category during the desk-based mapping.

3.1.1.3 Language

The required *Language* subcategory, when completed, predominantly states “English” with some lesser occurrences of “multi-language”.

3.1.1.4 GDPR/Sensitive Data Evaluation

In terms of having requirements for maintaining *GDPR* or having some evaluation for *Sensitive Data*, this was highlighted by one compiler as being potentially misinterpreted, because one could link *GDPR* to both the data themselves, or the depositor of the datasets. In any case, many disciplines either do not accept “sensitive data” (e.g. Food Sciences, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics) or are *GDPR*-compliant, but over half the individual

repositories do not have any information available. Surprisingly, in the disciplines that should account for sensitive data concerns – Linguistics and the Social Sciences – there is a dearth of GDPR requirements.

3.1.1.5 Reproduction Proof

For the final subcategory of *Contextual Data Quality*, i.e. *Reproduction proof*, the information is fragmented and no information is available for Linguistics, little for Earth & Environmental Sciences where provenance tracking is sometimes mentioned, and only for half the Life Sciences. Many entries across all repositories simply state “yes”, but some documents from Social Sciences and High-Energy Physics do provide some further details that include information on transparent versioning, audit trails, and environment recreation.

3.1.1.6 Contextual Data Quality – Summary

For *Contextual Data Quality*, there are notable gaps for describing *Data Rights/Consent held for Publication*, where there is very fragmented information available or reference is made to existing terms or policies which may provide more details. It is also clear that stipulating both the *Required Documentation* and *Reproduction proof of data* is fragmented across all disciplines. Reproduction proof information may be required within Methodology sections in accompanying documentation (e.g. README files) and thus may not have been accurately captured in the data collection.

3.1.2 Technical Data Quality

This category includes the following subcategories: *Data Type*, *File Format*, *File Size/Dataset Size*, *File Quantity*, and if there are requirements for *Checksums/Data Integrity*. Information coverage in this category is comprehensive due to the targeted activity of the repositories or communities (e.g. they accept data for deposit), although Social Sciences and Linguistics have markedly less information.

3.1.2.1 Data Type

For the subcategory *Data Type*, all subjects excluding Social Sciences have nearly complete information coverage. As expected, the types of data serve the individual discipline needs, and broadly fall into experimental, computational (e.g. models, simulation models, and DNA barcoding) and observational (e.g. seismological, sensor, specimen) data types, with some entries of classification/nomenclature datasets, survey and interview data (e.g. linguistics videos, texts). There are some inconsistencies for how data type is reported – this is due to both the different usage of the phrase across disciplines, and also how data type might be used by data stewards or curators. The Food Sciences, for example, describe how the data are stored (e.g. in documents or datasets), while Life Sciences variably uses “experimental”, “binary”, “text files”, etc., and Earth & Environmental Sciences uses very discipline-specific terms (e.g. “geochemical”, “seismic”).

3.1.2.2 File Format

One of the more scrutinized parameters is *File Format*, and all disciplines record extensive information across this subcategory. The requirements for *File Format* are heterogeneous, and vary broadly between repositories or communities that have stipulated format requirements and those that document which file formats are generally accepted and used by the community. File formats requirements thus are structured for most repositories into “preferred” file format lists, and notably concrete lists of “non-preferred” file formats are less well documented (an example of the latter can be found for the [Pangaea.de](https://pangaea.de) repository; ID32). Some repositories (e.g. ID44, [Clarin.eu](https://clarin.eu); ID34, <https://archive.mpi.nl/tla>) make further distinctions for “preferred” file formats that will be supported for LTDP (including format migration), whereas other file formats can only be guaranteed for a set period of time (e.g. 10 years) with minimal-to-no plans for format migration (e.g. bit-stream preservation only). Many disciplines have recommended formats that are generally dominated by binary and text-based formats, which are also open and non-proprietary. The physical and life science disciplines (e.g. Earth & Environmental Sciences, Climate Simulations, High-Energy Physics, and Life Sciences & Bioinformatics) often require binary formats such as NetCDF, various image formats (e.g. JPG, TIFF), and a collection of text-based formats (e.g. TXT, XML, YAML, ROOT, JSON, CSV, TSV, FASTA), or store their data

within relational databases (e.g. SQL), whereas the Food Sciences are dominated by PDF files. Linguistics-related repositories, due to the widespread use of interview data, have specific requirements for the resulting audio, video, and image files and generally stipulate open, uncompressed formats to best preserve the file quality. The Social Sciences are dominated by statistical file formats, with SPSS files highly recommended, in addition to open formats for text-based and binary file formats (the latter generally for images).

3.1.2.3 File Size/Dataset Size and File Quantity

The physical and life sciences generally have similar, yet fragmented, requirements for *File Size/Dataset Size* and *File Quantity*; for the former, either GB-scale file limits or no restrictions seems to be common (with no restrictions being common in the Life Sciences communities that allow data deposition), while the latter appears to have no restrictions at all. Both Linguistics and the Social Sciences have very sparse information with only a single entry each that indicate 10s of GB scale for individual and dataset sizes.

3.1.2.4 Checksums/Data Integrity

The final subcategory *Checksums/Data Integrity* has fragmented information, where there is an almost total absence of information for Food Sciences and Linguistics, but approximately 50% of the repositories and communities within Climate Simulations, Earth & Environmental Sciences, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, and Social Sciences indicate some level of data integrity checks. Most of these are a simple positive “yes” response, but there are some notes of “highly curated” and reporting of specific integrity checks such as CF checker (ID23) and md5 checksums (ID22).

3.1.2.5 Technical Data Quality – Summary

Although *Technical Data Quality* enjoys robust reporting across most disciplines in the subcategories, information regarding *File Size/Dataset Size*, *File Quantity*, and *Checksums/Data Integrity* remains fragmented and should be registered as a significant requirement gap.

3.1.3 Metadata Quality

This category includes the following subcategories: *Metadata Standards*, *Controlled Vocabulary*, *License*, *PID*, *PID Granularity*, *Access ± Embargo ± Restrictions*, and *Technical and Administrative Metadata in addition to Description*.

3.1.3.1 Metadata Standards

Metadata Standards are robustly reported across all disciplines excluding High-Energy Physics. For the former, the domain-agnostic Dublin Core, DataCite, DCAT and schema.org metadata vocabularies are reported in several disciplines (Earth & Environmental Sciences, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, Linguistics, and Social Sciences). Discipline-specific metadata standards are also used, in particular for the Earth & Environmental Sciences (e.g. ISO 19115, StationXML), Food Sciences (EuroFIR, Metrofood), Life Sciences & Bioinformatics (e.g. Darwin Core, EML, BOLD, MixS), Social Sciences (e.g. DDI), and Linguistics (e.g. CMDI, TEI). No metadata standard was reported for High-Energy Physics.

3.1.3.2 Controlled Vocabulary

Controlled Vocabulary, which can be either discipline-specific or operate across disciplines, appear to be most prevalent for the Life Sciences (e.g. ChEBI, NCBI) and the Earth & Environmental Sciences (e.g. EnVO, WoRMS). The choice of vocabularies for other disciplines (Climate Simulations, Food Sciences) appears to be less diverse but more harmonized within the repositories.

3.1.3.3 License

License requirements and recommendations for published datasets are well defined across all disciplines, with open licences being preferred with a strong prevalence of Creative Commons (creativecommons.org) licences being identified. Discipline-specific licenses are listed for Earth & Environmental Sciences (e.g. BSRN-1.0 for ID32; <https://bsrn.awi.de/data/conditions-of-data-release/>) and Linguistics (e.g. the CLARIN-RES and

CLARIN-ACA listed in ID34; <https://www.clarin.eu/content/licenses-and-clarin-categories>). Where extensive use of code and software occurs for a given discipline (e.g. Social Sciences), open software licences are also given (for example, Apache 2.0 for ID5, GNU GPL-3.0 for ID32; <https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>; <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>).

3.1.3.4 Persistent Identifiers

Persistent Identifiers are documented at both dataset and more granular levels. Most disciplines report DOIs with no indication of granularity, which could be interpreted to indicate at a dataset level. Some disciplines that operate with registration objects (e.g. physical samples, stations, barcodes) can also include sample registration PIDs (e.g. IGSN for Earth & Environmental Sciences; EC for Life Sciences & Bioinformatics).

3.1.3.5 Access, Embargo and Restrictions

Information regarding *Access, Embargo and Restrictions* is fragmented and heterogeneous across all disciplines, and can vary from user-defined embargoes or restrictions on data access, to where data releases are centrally controlled by an organization (notable for the High-Energy Physics communities). There are only few examples of clear repository-defined embargo periods: the Earth & Environmental Sciences Pangaea repository (ID32; <https://www.pangaea.de/>) enforces a maximum time period of two years to password-protect data, whereas the Life Sciences repository IntAct (ID38; <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/intact/home>) requires that data is published openly when any associated papers are published.

3.1.3.6 Technical and Administrative Metadata in addition to Description

The final subcategory *Technical and Administrative Metadata* extends “in addition to Description” metadata, and is poorly documented across all disciplines. There are mentions of ensuring Management metadata is recorded with regards to funding, recording station infrastructure metadata (Earth & Environmental Sciences), experimental metadata (High-Energy Physics), and specimen metadata (Life Sciences).

3.1.3.7 Metadata Quality – Summary

Information for *Metadata Quality* is robust, but overall there is a gap of recording the granularity of *PIDs*, and additional requirements for *Administrative and Technical Metadata*. Food Sciences and High-Energy Physics are less robustly documented than the other disciplines, and this requires some attention.

3.1.4 Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities

This category includes the following subcategories: *Deposit Criteria, Choice of Repository, Backups, Retention Policies, Compliance with Framework/Policies, Machine Readable/API Access to Dataset, Financial Burden Plan, Repository Exit Strategy (Long Term Sustainability), and Versioning Support*.

3.1.4.1 Deposit Criteria

Where disciplines have active repositories that accept data for deposition, *Deposit Criteria* information is robustly documented including the following conditions: data must fall within the discipline-specific scope; the depositor must be a community member (e.g. have a valid log-in for the given repository); and the data must meet specific (format, technical, administrative) criteria specified by the repository. Regarding the latter, several repositories stipulate that only data from certain geographic locations (e.g. Irish Social Science Data Archive; ID49), or monitoring stations (e.g. the Copernicus satellites for C3S Climate data store; ID66), or submitted by organisations (e.g. the Global Biodiversity Information Facility; ID7) may be deposited.

3.1.4.2 Choice of Repository

The subcategory *Choice of Repository* is sparsely documented, partially because some identified repositories are in fact the chosen repository (and stipulated, for example, by funding agencies or journals), but where data does exist, for example in High-Energy Physics (ID27 and 31), well-established repositories such as [HEPdata.net](https://hepdata.net) or [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org) are listed.

3.1.4.3 Backups and Retention Policies

The *Backups* and *Retention Policies* subcategories have only limited information coverage across most disciplines, with only one entry for Linguistics from ID34 (The Language Archive). Where documented in T3.1, accessible information is heterogeneous and includes responses ranging from a simple positive “yes”, to mentions of a dark archive (for High-Energy Physics ID28), to regular cyclical updates (e.g. ID7-8 in Life Sciences) for data backups. Information for retention policies is similar, with vague responses ranging from “yes” to “long term preservation” to “forever”, but also more concrete time frames (10s of years, e.g. ID34).

3.1.4.4 Compliance with Framework/Policies

Information for *Compliance with Frameworks/Policies* is fragmented and again broadly split into two groups, one which is discipline-specific and the other more generalist. The former includes entities such as INSPIRE (https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/index_en) for spatial data (ID61,65,66), and EMBL-EBI (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>) for Life Sciences & Bioinformatics (ID5,6,21), whereas generalist compliance frameworks commonly include mentions of ISO standards, OAI (<http://www.oais.info/>), FAIR (gofair.com), and the CoreTrustSeal certificate (<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>). Repositories and communities falling within the Social Sciences and Linguistics disciplines also record adherence to GDPR, as would be expected due to the prevalence of person-identifying, and in many cases sensitive, data within these subjects, as well as the CARE principles (<https://www.gida-global.org/care>) covering Indigenous data.

3.1.4.5 Machine Readable/API Access to Dataset

In terms of *Machine Readable/API Access to Dataset*, across all disciplines, it is commonly indicated that plans are in place, with API frequently mentioned, and metadata harvesting through OAI-PMH. Both Climate Simulations and Earth & Environmental Sciences also use OGC for spatial data. The Linguistics and Social Sciences further stipulate that only metadata harvesting is permitted.

3.1.4.6 Financial Burden Plan

Plans regarding *Financial Burden* for the various repositories and communities vary substantially both between and within disciplines, with most information referring to financial support from host institutions, national-level grants in various countries (e.g. Canada, Germany), international grants (e.g. European Commission, Wellcome Trust), or sponsorship or charitable contributions from private foundations.

3.1.4.7 Repository Exit Strategy (Long Term Sustainability)

Similar to other subcategories (e.g. *Backups*), *Repository Exit Strategy* (or *Long Term Sustainability*) can host brief, uninformative information such as “yes” or “no plans”, to mentions of cloud or mirrored services (especially commonly reported for the Life Sciences & Bioinformatics). The most detailed and thorough plans can be found for several repositories in Linguistics and the Social Sciences, which describe collaborations with external institutions, other archives, or network nodes that will take over the responsibility and data in case of repository cessation (ID34, 47-48).

3.1.4.8 Versioning Support

Similarly, *Versioning Support* is also answered by a simple “yes”, to more concrete timelines (between 4-8 weeks), to complete plans about version updates accompanying database updates with respect to additional curation, updated metadata, or changes for better LTDP (e.g. ID47). It could be assumed here that two types of versioning are being recorded, one where the simple positive responses indicate that updates of datasets are tracked and thus receive updated versions, to another type that is led by updates to Database services and quality assurances (e.g. software updates that can include new standards and features; e.g. ID14).

3.1.4.9 Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities – Summary

Significant gaps in this category include a more coherent and comprehensive standard for delineating how repositories will be backed up (including frequency and long term plans), and what compliance frameworks will be used. Additionally, information surrounding exit strategies should be in place across all disciplines.

3.1.5 Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs

This category includes the following subcategories: *Generalist vs. Specialist Curators*, *Level of Curation*, *Reassessment Schedule*, and *Original and Access Copy of Material*. Aside from information regarding curation processes for the repositories and communities, this category is lacking robust information.

3.1.5.1 Generalist vs. Specialist Curators

Most repositories or communities indicate that they support some level of curation, but curation appears to be notably lacking for Food Sciences, High-Energy Physics and Linguistics. Where curation is supported, specialist curators are overwhelmingly predominant and only one generalist curator is indicated by ID6.

3.1.5.2 Level of Curation

Curation level for the repositories has been assessed using the Core Trust Seal levels of Curation and Preservation (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2024) and includes the lowest level Z (zero curation), to D (deposit compliance), C (initial curation), and finally A, which includes the requirements of D and C plus active preservation. The recorded curation level across all disciplines is variable from A to Z, but it appears that level “A” is most common (especially for the Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, and Social Sciences).

3.1.5.3 Reassessment Schedule

Information for the *Reassessment Schedule* is extremely sparse, with the few entries that exist simply stating “yes” to indications of more regular (but undefined) checks.

3.1.5.4 Original and Access Copy of Material

The final subcategory is if *Original and Access Copies of Material* are retained, and mirroring the previous subcategory, the little information that does exist again is either simple “yes” or “strongly recommended” responses.

3.1.5.5 Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs – Summary

In general, there is a significant information gap regarding whether data in the discipline-specific repositories are reassessed and what kind of data copies are retained.

3.2 Stand-Alone Interviews

Eighteen interviews were carried out and transcribed as introduced in Section 2.2, the categorical output was mapped for each discipline in T3.1_Interviews_Requirements_V1 and manually assessed into a summary for each of the five main components of the Re-use Fitness model in T3.1_Interviews_Synthesized_Requirements_V1. Sections 3.2.1–3.2.5 draw the consensus at a cross-disciplinary level, emphasising the resulting commonalities and issues from interviewed researchers and repository managers. Note that due to the more flexible and less categorical nature of the interview methodology, compared to the desk-based mapping, we do not present the results per subcategory.

3.2.1 Contextual Data Quality

This subsection covers the synthesis of subcategories *Required Documentation*, *Data Rights/Consent held for publication*, *Language*, *GDPR/Sensitive Data Evaluation*, *Reproduction proof for data*, and *Comments*.

Most disciplines emphasise the importance of implemented metadata standards to ensure data quality. This is enforced by some repositories by the use of e.g. spreadsheet templates (Excel or tab-separated files) to secure consistency. Still, many disciplines find metadata quality challenging due to incompleteness, particularly among older datasets or when data is captured in unique contexts like field recordings. Integration and comparability of data between databases is also highlighted by some disciplines as problematic. Related provenance information is in many cases captured in deposited metadata or through practices by the repositories. Post deposition, however, legal issues are experienced in High-Energy Physics and Social

Sciences for data licensing and data ownership. In the former case data ownership is transferred to the repository upon data submission, while in the latter case licensing agreements were often made with individuals rather than institutions, leading to complications when those individuals are no longer available.

Repositories play a central role by providing documentation and guidelines for researchers to be successful in data deposition. This is largely expected by researchers where open communication with repository contacts is critical for clarification and support. However, guidelines on the FAIRification of data being deposited is often lacking for researchers seeking improved findability and reusability of their data. Ethical handling of data is recurring across disciplines when dealing with sensitive data. However, though not as prevalent in some disciplines, consent mechanisms are usually implemented. Yet, ensuring proper handling through the CARE principles is seen as challenging as there is a need to balance ethical considerations, cultural sensitivities, and LTDP with practical issues like metadata recovery, tailored access, and non-anonymizable data. These challenges are compounded by the lack of standardized procedures and the diverse needs of communities and researchers.

3.2.2 Technical Data Quality

This subsection covers the synthesis of subcategories *Data Type, File Format, File size/Dataset Size, File Quantity, Checksums/Data Integrity, and Comments*.

The data types and file formats vary across disciplines, but there is a clear preference towards using open file formats to ensure accessibility and interoperability. Proprietary formats are often seen as challenging from both researcher and repository perspectives, relating to cost and compatibility. Researchers in Climate Simulations and Linguistics experience challenges with format changes (e.g., compressed files) and the restriction on acceptable formats by repositories. Guidelines for monitoring standards for the migration to other file formats are reported as a need. However, many repositories strive to offer interoperable formats to facilitate data sharing and reuse. This is also a request by researchers in order to download data in suitable formats for their tools or workflows.

Many of the interviewed disciplines report generating hundreds of GBs of data, with large files (e.g., multimedia and binary as mentioned) causing issues during archiving. File size is linked with integrity checksums, a practice many disciplines highlight concerns about. Integrity checks vary by means of implementations in some reported disciplines. However, duplicated data (multiple copies of the same dataset) is reported as an added challenge in Food Sciences. Stable funding and infrastructure for data storage are recurring concerns across disciplines, also among depositing researchers.

3.2.3 Metadata Quality

This subsection covers the synthesis of subcategories *Metadata Standard, Controlled Vocabulary, License, PID, PID granularity, Access ± Embargo ± Restrictions, Technical and Administrative Metadata in addition to Description, and Comments*.

As metadata are vital in describing a digital data object, most disciplines have adopted standards fitting their line of work and formats used. Long-term preservation of metadata and their quality, however, is seen as challenging. This is due to several reasons including evolving internal systems and standards, the lack of detail in metadata provided during the deposition process, which requires manual completion and therefore is time-consuming in some disciplines. As a result, many repositories across the interviewed disciplines see the need to curate deposited data. This is carried out to fit their metadata model, fill information gaps and include other services like checks on data quality, metadata completeness, and adherence to standards.

Improved workflows, training, tools, and automation of metadata annotation are generally sought after by both researchers and repository managers. Repositories further update their metadata models as the discipline

evolves, integrating controlled vocabularies and ontologies to standardize metadata fields for improved interoperability. However, varying levels of maturity and adoption of standards challenge interoperability between repositories in some disciplines. Updates made by repositories strive to meet the needs of the community. Still, the awareness and importance of metadata standards is often missed by researchers, and these standards are not always followed strictly, leading to inconsistencies across repositories in disciplines. Many repositories have review processes on submitted metadata quality, with some disciplines, e.g. Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, operating with minimum requirements for subject-specific datasets. Better community engagement is mentioned as a way to make standards more widely adopted to improve metadata consistency. In Life Sciences & Bioinformatics mistakes in metadata can spread from major databases (like those in the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, insdc.org) to other tools and services that rely on them, which can lead to problems where incorrect information is trusted and used in further research.

On the technical side, licensing generally follows Creative Commons or Open Government Licenses, with some researchers preferring non-commercial licenses. Guidance on licensing of, and access to sensitive data is not well covered in some disciplines, but relevant repositories have implemented multi-level access controls to cover various request situations. This solution is particularly mentioned within Linguistics with regards to ethical considerations where the openness of data, e.g., for vulnerable groups, person-identifying data, and minority communities is noted as a recurring challenge. Delayed access, often referred to as embargo periods, is common practice in the repositories interviewed and span the involved disciplines.

The use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) is also widespread among disciplines for datasets and collections and is largely recognised as vital to ensure long-term identification and accessibility. Based on statements from a researcher in Social Sciences, there is a desire to get assigned unique PIDs by automatic means, indicating a bottleneck in workflows.

3.2.4 Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities

This subsection covers the synthesis of subcategories *Deposit Criteria, Choice of Repository, Backups, Retention Policies, Compliance with Frameworks/Policies, Machine-Readable/API Access to Dataset, Governance, Financial Burden Plan, Repository Exit Strategy (Long-Term Sustainability), Support of Versioning in the Repository, and Comments*.

Upon data deposition, repositories express criteria for data to be considered suitable for archiving. The most common criteria is metadata completeness and the adherence to specific file formats as these ensure data usability and discoverability across the disciplines. On the other hand, researchers tend to choose suitable repositories based on community norms, established practices, funders, journal requirements, trusted institutions, but also favour indicators such as support for FAIR principles, the use of PIDs, and effective communication with the repository. Sometimes a mix of generalist repositories (e.g., Zenodo, GitHub) and domain-specific repositories are chosen, depending on the nature of their data and convenience. The ease of submission, like automated upload, metadata management, and seamless versioning are all convenient features desired by depositing researchers. Version control is seen as challenging in some disciplines due to rapidly evolving data types and standards. Most disciplines emphasize the importance of LTDP, with repositories guaranteeing a minimum retention period (e.g., 10 years) but aiming for much longer durations up to 30 years or even indefinite. From the researchers' perspective the retention period is also a consideration when choosing a repository. However, it is not commonplace for researchers to evaluate formal certification statuses as a way to choose trustworthy repositories.

For a repository to maintain LTDP capabilities it relies on a robust infrastructure and well established funding sources. Multi-site redundancy, where stored data is spread in copies at multiple geographical locations, is

common practice across disciplines to ensure data storage is safe. Some repositories use tape archives or other in-house mechanisms to ensure data safety and integrity. The management of diverse and large datasets, up to petabyte ranges, is mentioned as logistically challenging and strains on the financial aspect of the repositories. Following this, stable funding for LTDP is a recurring challenge mentioned by many repository managers. There is a wide reliance on short-term funding cycles which does not provide the assurance needed for true LTDP and remains as a potential threat to the existence of deposited data. In the case of an operational shutdown or funding cessation for a repository, it is also very likely there is no formal exit strategy. In most cases, exit strategies are lacking or underdeveloped for repositories across disciplines.

3.2.5 Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs

This subsection covers the synthesis of subcategories *Generalist vs. Specialist Curators*, *Level of Curation*, *Reassessment Schedule*, *Original and Access Copy of Material*, *Program-Related Tools/Tech Watch*, *Motivation and Attitudes*, *Training and Dialogue with repository*, and *Comments*.

As community resources, repositories are central in servicing the involved disciplines over time. A clear motivation lies in the scientific and societal value of preserving data for long-term use, as mentioned by researchers and repository managers. Still, some repositories operate with small teams, limiting their ability to engage in larger projects or provide extensive support to researchers. Most repositories engage with their communities to some extent, e.g., through workshops, surveys, and user groups while also providing training material in several formats. Even so, researchers in some disciplines describe competing priorities and a lack of time as issues when engaging with repositories.

Those repositories with data occasionally used by scholars outside their designated communities can find it difficult to meet cross-disciplinary needs, which pertain to issues like data formats, languages, and differing standards. An example is found in Climate Simulations repositories when data are retrieved and used by researchers in Social Sciences. There is, however, a consensus among researchers and repository managers that outreach activities stimulate data archiving, improve the skills needed for depositing data, and emphasize the importance of metadata and documentation for reuse purposes by communities. A strengthening of this communication, through surveys and user groups, is mentioned as a way for the repositories to better align with researchers and community needs. Even with existing training materials on data preparation, metadata requirements, and functionalities, there is a need for researchers to receive additional guidance to fully utilize repositories. The increased complexity of data and repository functionalities in some disciplines makes it challenging for researchers to stay updated on available features. Some researchers additionally express the need for clearer guidelines on data acceptance, how data are to be deposited, and how updates are handled.

Repositories carry out several services related to technology watch, such as curation, file conversion, and the integration of AI assistance. While some interviewed researchers highlight the need for extended file conversion functionalities, a few repositories note the challenges of scaling these services to meet community needs. Additionally, evolving standards for data preservation and the lack of LTDP policies and reappraisal strategies are recurring issues, further complicating the reappraisal of older datasets in particular. Many repositories have not established systematic reappraisal processes, but tend to be ad hoc or reactive to specific needs such as metadata updates. While some repositories have mechanisms for updating or creating new versions of datasets (Earth & Environmental Sciences and Climate Simulations), others focus on preserving all data without significant reappraisal efforts (Life Sciences & Bioinformatics and Linguistics).

4 Discussion

Realizing the real-world working environments and challenges with regard to LTDP and DOQ in the academic landscape is vital to the EOSC EDEN project, and forms the core of WP3 (“Discipline-specific requirements, validation and future use”). Two methodologies for investigating discipline-specific LTDP and DOQ, i.e. desk-

based mapping and stand-alone interviews, have been developed and executed by T3.1 in M1 – M6. In addition, T3.1 has built a set of discipline-specific questions for the WP1 survey on identification, appraisal and selection of digital data for LTDP, which will be reported in M12 via D1.1. This way of studying how disciplinary communities implement and describe a predefined set of requirements makes it possible to identify commonalities and specificities, and also to assess various maturity levels.

The main outcome of M1 – M6 is an initial overview of LTDP and DOQ practices within and across the seven early-adopter disciplines represented in the project. While the data collection cannot report the complete diversity of existing requirements, gaps, and needs within a given discipline, it still offers a broad starting point we can build on in WP1 and WP2 and in later iterations of data collection in WP3.

Before addressing main observed commonalities and needs in Sections 4.2 – 4.3, we use Section 4.1 to discuss challenges related to the heterogeneous information landscape. Section 4.4 offers a set of perspectives for the next phases of T3.1 inside EOSC EDEN.

4.1 A Heterogeneous Information Landscape

A challenging aspect of T3.1 is directly related to the fundamental differences that exist between different discipline-specific repositories with respect to LTDP and DOQ documentation and also dedicated support services. Some well-established and mature repositories have clear stand-alone documents or wikis adhering to established standards, as well as data scientist experts, developers, or digital preservationists able to provide clear and abundant information regarding all facets of LTDP and DOQ. This can vary from providing detailed lists of file formats on repository wikis (e.g. Pangaea for the Earth & Environmental Sciences, and CLARIN for Linguistics), to having detailed guides on access levels and licensing (e.g. UK Data Service for the Social Sciences).

Conversely, repositories that operate on a more reduced scale and are led by scholars in the discipline-specific field may not have robustly documented policies for LTDP and DOQ. We note, however, that this observation was not formally captured by the desk-based mapping and is based on a limited number of interviews. In these cases, knowledge and implementation of standard LTDP and DOQ requirements has the potential to be less present, for various reasons. First, a small operating staff may not always have the capacity to engage with relevant networks or other infrastructures from which they could benefit to improve their LTDP- and DOQ-related services. Further, smaller, scholar-led repositories often collaborate with and depend on other institutional units for archival or IT-related services, which may lead to the different parties neither seeing nor understanding the holistic view. Thus, although these smaller community-driven repositories may excel at certain tasks that are critical for the type of data they work with (e.g. detailed discipline-specific metadata or data documentation), other more technical requirements and services can be more typically uneven (e.g. lack of systematised community and technology watch). One example is the GeoRoc repository that has a long standing reputation for being an excellent data source (e.g. sourced from published manuscripts), but is now in its infancy with regard to data intake and active deposition and will naturally require adherence to robust and sustainable standards. Another is The Language Archive, which for many years has been collaborating with the [DOBES programme](#) (from 2000 onwards) and thus has long experience with Indigenous and endangered languages; In this repository, knowledge about local norms for handling such data is strong, but a recent Core Trust Seal application shows the expressed need for aligning repository policies with recent legal and ethical frameworks such as GDPR and CARE (The Language Archive, 2024).

Finally, many smaller repositories are closely linked to specific research departments or institutes, which can be advantageous because the designated community remains close. However, if the repository governance lacks detailed expertise on LTDP and DOQ and more heavily relies on faculty staff with little daily engagement

with repository practices, this may lead to an increased responsibility of the repository personnel to ensure the implementation of strategies and roadmaps aligning with current standards.

Working with the desk-based mapping and the stand-alone interviews has revealed that although the seven early-adopter disciplines and their methods for engaging with data and other digital objects are very diverse, there are certain commonalities emerging from the material. There are also some discipline-specific practices or challenges that should be investigated for other disciplines dealing with similar data types or data-type-related aspects. In what follows, we concentrate on some main commonalities that are identified in this first round of data collection, which, to emphasize again, represents only a part of the landscape.

4.2 Commonalities and Specificities in Existing Requirements

Within the area of *Contextual Data Quality*, all seven early-adopter disciplines highlight the importance of data provenance information along with contextual metadata (e.g. a ReadMe file, detailed documentation) for data reuse and method replication. Another commonality in this area regards dealing with sensitive data: disciplines that handle sensitive data regularly (Linguistics, Social Sciences) have implemented consent mechanisms. Yet, ensuring proper ethical handling through e.g. the CARE principles is generally seen as challenging. One specificity that stands out in the Contextual Data Quality section regards data rights: In High-Energy Physics ownership of data is often transferred to repositories upon upload, with legal teams handling disputes.

Regarding *Technical Data Quality*, a commonality across the disciplines is a clear preference for open and standardized file formats. This move away from proprietary formats is explicitly mentioned by High-Energy Physics, and, in the case of a climate data repository, non-proprietary file formats are even mandatory. Numerous accepted file formats are listed within the existing recommendations and guidelines, with the most common being CSV, FASTA, JPG, JSON, NETCDF, PDF, ROOT, SPSS, SQL, STATA, TSV, TXT, WAV, XML, and YAML, and also DOCX and XLSX as proprietary file formats. Another commonality across the discipline-specific guidelines is the lack of an explicitly stated restriction of large datasets, file sizes, or file numbers. Whether this means an actual lack of restriction or is – more probably – a gap in the guidelines is uncertain. Another issue in this area of Technical Data Quality is highlighted by the Food Sciences (in contrast to the other disciplines), where duplicated data is a problem to be solved.

Regarding *Metadata Quality*, the use of persistent identifiers is common across the disciplines. DOIs are widely used, but also other types of persistent identifiers. Another common cross-disciplinary practice is the use of various metadata standards (both discipline-specific and agnostic) and – to a lesser extent – controlled vocabularies to attain consistency in repositories. Almost all repositories use Creative Commons (CC) licences, and software licenses – when used – are open source. Especially within Linguistics (although this is known within Life Sciences & Bioinformatics as well) the use of multiple access levels and licenses to protect sensitive data is highlighted, which is less emphasized in other disciplines.

In the area of *Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities*, most repositories across the disciplines have clear deposit criteria that stipulate data must be discipline- and format-specific. Usually, the depositor must be individually registered or a society/community member and has to log in, in order to deposit digital objects. Most repositories are machine-readable and provide API access to the datasets. The majority of them also support versioning of their data. Most disciplines emphasize the importance of LTDP, with repositories guaranteeing a minimum retention period (e.g., 10 years in Climate Simulations) but aiming for much longer durations up to 30 years (Earth & Environmental Sciences) or even indefinite. Redundant storage capacity is needed where additional backups exist as a protection measure against data loss (as documented for the Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, Linguistics). Certification of the repositories is deemed important especially within Linguistics and Social Sciences and seems less prioritized within Climate Simulations and Food Sciences. It

is noteworthy, however, that repository administrators consider certification more important than the interviewed researchers did. The latter are more interested in usability aspects, data quality and user support than certification, which are notably not key topics for certification at present. The motivation of researchers for depositing their data is mostly external across the communities, e.g. made mandatory by funders or journals (Climate Simulations, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics). Exit strategies of the repositories are more formalised in Linguistics and High-Energy Physics, but other repositories have no clear plans.

Regarding their *Preservation Objective and Designated Community Needs*, almost all repositories use specialized curators, although the level of expertise in LTDP varies. Curation depth varies between repositories where some employ highly trained curators, while others may rely on community curation or self-deposit. Some disciplines prioritize raw and intermediate data preservation, while others focus on processed data. A common feature across the discipline-specific repositories is their community engagement. This happens in various ways, e.g. via conferences, workshops, guidance materials, user group feedback, or surveys. Also, the repositories usually have an ethical and/or legal framework in place for storing sensitive data (Linguistics, Social Sciences, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics).

4.3 Emerging Needs in Discipline-Specific Repositories and Communities

In this section, we draw attention to the main needs observed across the desk-based mapping and the interviews.

4.3.1 Contextual Data Quality

The most critical needs for this category are ensuring that robust data documentation can support preservation and data utility. There is also a strong need to ensure that sensitive data – including data that is person-identifying, contain commercial links, or have security concerns –, as well as data involving Indigenous communities, receive appropriate consideration. Although all disciplines indicate that dataset-accompanying documentation is required, both the form and content of this documentation is undefined. It is strongly recommended to provide standardised, accessible, and comprehensive methods for applying documentation to datasets, intended to exist alongside standardized metadata schema. Arising specifically from the interview results is a conflation of metadata documentation vs. data-specific documentation, where the latter provides detailed information on data provenance (e.g. methodologies, codebooks, re-use), such as a stand-alone ReadMe file. There is a strong need to create an inclusive, standardized documentation tool (e.g. interactive “ReadMe” document builder) that has the possibility to be scaled both within, and across, discipline-specific needs.

- The tool mentioned above should also be comprehensible for both depositors and repositories, and contain explicit requirements for ascertaining data rights and obligations, noting that different disciplines will have different obligations and rights agreements.
- The robustness of metadata standards in older datasets, or datasets involving unique data capture contexts (e.g. recordings), must be improved and brought to a standardized level that allows for LTDP, understandability, and access that is as open as possible but as closed as necessary. Automated tools that are able to process older datasets plus their documentation – including potentially fragmented and incomplete metadata and stand-alone documentation files – and subsequently equip them with robust, standardized documentation, metadata and licences, are required.
- Awareness about GDPR concerns surrounding sensitive data, as well as consideration of the CARE principles must increase, especially for disciplines focussed in the Humanities and Social Sciences. However, universal tools to ensure GDPR-compliance and/or CARE-adherence are recommended to be rolled out across all disciplines. Some disciplines state that sensitive data is not handled and therefore legal guidelines such as GDPR requirements are not applicable. Similarly, the impact of some

research on Indigenous persons societies, environments and spaces may not be immediately recognized, and therefore the CARE requirements are not considered. However, growing novel cross-disciplinary research topics (e.g. medical geology, integrations of computational and medical sciences), as well as the increasing recognition that much scientific research is being conducted within Indigenous societies, environments and spaces, requires widespread adoption of these policies.

4.3.2 Technical Data Quality

The consensus drawn from interviews and the desk-based mapping shows the effective management of file formats is critical for ensuring LTDP, accessibility, and interoperability across discipline-specific repositories. This varies from standardizing acceptable file types to addressing challenges with proprietary formats, multimedia integration, and data migration.

- There is a need to systematize ways of monitoring preferred file types that are considered standard, and/or acceptable for file migration and LTDP. Likewise, file types can be tagged as not acceptable e.g., if proprietary or going against common practices. The level of standardisation may vary between disciplines and repositories, and on a case-by-case level, and should not be limited to black and white guidelines, but take into account recommended and non-advisable format types.
- Small repositories have shown the need for explicit guidance on file formats to sufficiently fulfill community needs.
- There are expectations by communities that file formats should be easily integrable with common disciplinary workflows. Thus, there is a need to ensure that tools and services can interoperate with the entire range of discipline-specific file types, with particular attention to specialized file types. In cases such as Climate Simulations where repositories have users from other disciplines, e.g. Social Sciences, interoperable formats need further considerations and optional guidelines on how file formats can be adapted outside the main discipline.
- Multimedia formats are used in several disciplines with potential challenges regarding storage, integration, and formatting. There is a need for lists and guidelines on acceptable audio and video file types and how to manage these through e.g. creation, compression, editing and tagging.
- There are examples of mixed use between open and proprietary file formats from working with the seven disciplines. Proprietary formats can be dependent on specific software and face challenges if applications are deprecated. However, many find it challenging to know which open formats are available and how to operate these in the respective discipline. This illustrates the need for an extensive public registry for open file formats and their specifications.²⁶
- Migration of data files, particularly larger sizes like hundreds of megabytes and above, run the risk of damaging file integrities. As many disciplines report managing such files, integrity checks need to be a scheduled process by running checksums on files. In addition, there should be a recommended file size(s) across disciplines, with specific preservation practices recommended for very large files.
- In some repositories duplicate data exists but with no management plan to address the issue. Duplications strain storage capabilities and may cause confusion among researchers. This calls for optional recommendations in managing technical data quality by deduplication.
- Technical requirements for LTDP of raw and intermediate data is mentioned as a need in some disciplines. In some cases the raw and intermediate data may be demanding and costly to store and must be dealt with in the context of the repository's storage capabilities, their funding and discipline-

²⁶ Registries and lists of file formats already exist that can serve as starting point in this action, c.f. e.g. [PRONOM](#) and [DANS](#).

specific practices. It is therefore recommended that levels of processing should be considered in guidelines for repositories and addressed with relevant user groups.

4.3.3 Metadata Quality

Stemming from the learnings in the desk-based mapping and interviews, it is apparent that the main challenges arise from the ability of researchers to both understand and adhere to metadata standards, and also for metadata standards to interoperate between disciplines.

- Flexible, discipline-agnostic metadata standards (e.g. DCAT) are needed to facilitate interdisciplinary research, data discovery, and data package transfer between repositories.
- Direct communication between the repository and the depositor needs to be available, with increased communication about the implementation of, clarification/explanation of, and compliance with metadata standards. The communication or explanation needs can be expressed as both monitory, which includes repositories having one-on-one contact with depositors, and automated, with respect to improving workflows, standardizing metadata annotation and facilitating completeness.
- There need to be clear recommendations for non-CC licences when necessary. This includes the recommendation of a standard software license that is free, open, and interoperable such as the EU Commission-recommended [EURL](#). Furthermore, guidelines must be established for how to select licenses that facilitate optimization and accessibility for sensitive, person-identifying, and/or Indigenous data. Discipline-, geographic-, and organization-specific licences are commonly in use, and would benefit from semantic indexing and cataloguing to enhance both license understandability and data reusability.
- Recommendations and workflows are needed to increase granularity for PIDs – for example, at file-, sample-, and instrument-level.
- Standardized time recommendations for file restrictions, access control or embargoes are needed in order to strike a balance between FAIR requirements for data, publication requirements and researcher concerns surrounding open data sharing. A further need is for repositories to ensure the existence of clear channels of communication to discuss restricted or embargoed data (e.g. author and/or repository contact information that is not time-sensitive).

4.3.4 Trustworthy Digital Archive Capabilities

The results from the desk-based mapping and interviews have provided a clear need for establishment of standard, comprehensive, and mandatory policies for digital archive backups, retention policies, financial planning, exit strategies, and versioning support. Note that these are aspects not only relevant for repositories labelled “trustworthy” by the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects, but are applicable to repositories with different levels of maturity.

- Awareness of repository certification must be increased within the target researcher communities. The interviews in particular indicate that the choice of repository to deposit datasets, or for reuse purposes, is heavily swayed by factors such as common practices, stakeholder demands, and ease-of-use in the involved disciplines, running contrary selection based on repository certification which acts as a guarantee for trust and quality.
- Formal policies and strategies to ensure data backups, retention policies, long-term financial planning, and exit strategies are insufficient for most disciplines and must be established. Backups are an important task for many repositories, and concrete technical implementation plans (with options for transfer to third parties if necessary) that support data package transfer across all disciplines must be rolled out. Few infrastructures operate under sustainable funding models, where some repositories may receive funding from one or two close partner institutions, but at the same time lack a long-term strategy for operational upkeep and maintenance that can be in conflict with their guaranteed

retention period. Formal exit strategies with concrete plans, partners, and workflows must be established in order to prevent data loss and additionally have grave consequences for researchers.

- While most infrastructures have considered machine readability and have API access to their data, open data and metadata harvesting protocols should be standardized with improved documentation such as through use of OAI-PMH, or other well-established suitable protocols.
- Versioning needs better support towards appropriate logging within a repository, and in particular the transfer of version histories and logs when dataset packages are transferred to other repositories. This is reflected in the level of versioning by infrastructures and inconsistent knowledge by researchers concerning discipline specific practices. Versioning of data, metadata and the service framework of the repositories are the most common solutions encountered.

4.3.5 Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs

There are several critical challenges faced by repositories when considering policies and procedures surrounding data preservation and outreach to research communities.

- Although all disciplines indicate that expert curators are utilized across all disciplines, variability in the level of curation requires that a standard level of acceptable curation that enables LTDP and DOQ must be promoted.
- Across all disciplines, standardized and comprehensive strategic reappraisal and reassessment schedules and guidelines must be established and implemented. The existing tendency to follow long-standing practices or the simple statement that data will be preserved “forever” is inadequate and comprehensive strategies must be put in place.
- Regular, standard reappraisals and reassessment checks, that include methodologies for enhancement (e.g. file format, metadata enrichment), are required to ensure LDP and DOQ for both historical and legacy data, as well as relevant standards. The relevance of older data and standards is not sufficiently assessed across many disciplines, but can be highly relevant for state-of-the-art science that includes, for example, field recordings that capture linguistic variables, sampling of targeted organisms, or time-series climate data. Older data can be vital to understand temporal changes in many disciplines, and the rapid evolution of technology presents new challenges for both evaluating and supporting historical and legacy data plus standards.
- Concerning identifying needs in the designated community (community watch), developing a targeted, inclusive, and systematic approach to community engagement should be considered within the disciplines, preferably as a joint effort between repositories to reduce duplication of work. There are advantages but also challenges related to interaction strategies that limit focus to certain groups: While involving designated user groups can facilitate knowledge sharing and systematising of needs identified, it can be non-inclusive and lead to other community needs being missed.
- Researchers wish to deposit data efficiently and in line with good practice, and having access to an active support desk and/or a contact point inside the repository, where someone takes the time to answer, is strongly wanted. Interaction between repository personnel and depositor cannot be neglected, even when elaborated repository user guides exist. For the researcher, who often deposits data at a very irregular frequency, having someone with trustworthy digital repositories competencies who can give advice and answer questions, is highlighted as very important for trust and user experience. For the repository, this human contact point aids monitoring the needs in the community. Common repository personnel-directed FAQs within disciplines may improve and facilitate live guidance, as well as reducing time spent formulating advice and answers.

4.4 T3.1 Methodology: Perspectives

In Section 1.2 we detailed the purposes of this deliverable inside the EOSC EDEN project and showed how our work is connected to other tasks and actions in WP1, WP2, and WP3. The collection and analysis of data carried out in the present work have revealed existing requirements, gaps and needs in a rich variety of areas, and it is in the nature of the project that next iterations of data collections will prioritise fine-tuning and systematisation in the methodology, and more targeted topical focus. Concrete procedures will be identified in collaboration with our WP1 and WP2 partners.

Before we close this report, we mention two factors that may have affected the results in the current data material, and which need to be thoroughly evaluated before the next iteration of data collection in T3.1:

Timing: The initial plan was to perform the desk-based mapping prior to development of survey questions and interview guide, to allow the latter to complement and/or detail observations from the former. Given the necessary start-up phase of the project, work packages and tasks, and various task-internal and -external deadlines, we needed to create and complete the survey questions while simultaneously planning how to proceed in the desk-based mapping. In addition, it was necessary to develop and finalize the interview protocol while simultaneously analysing the results of the desk-based mapping. Future data collection endeavours should be better organised, and allocate ample time to permit better alignment of the actions with a more harmonious roll out of the data collection procedures.

Harmonisation: We decided to use the Re-use Fitness model as a frame for the overall categorisation of data from the desk-based mapping and the interviews. Although the data collection in these two methods was intended to be complimentary, the desk-based mapping spreadsheet – with its many subcategories – was created first. We discovered when attempting to map the interview data to this spreadsheet that some aspects of the interview data were less easily categorised into the rigid boxes of the desk-based mapping subcategories. The explanation is probably twofold; 1) that the desk-based mapping document lacked sufficient descriptions of subcategories, and 2) that the interviews were structured around a protocol with a more flexible approach, where some aspects are mentioned in different contexts (metadata being a prime example), where the level of detail and granularity is less present and consistent (in particular for some subcategories related to technical data quality and metadata quality), and where other nuances positively interfere (e.g. motivation, learning, interaction). When preparing future data collections in T3.1, we need to find ways of harmonising procedures and facilitating analysis, while at the same time making full use of the potential of the various types of data.

5 Summary

This report has presented the methodology and results from the first data collection within WP3 of EOSC EDEN, aimed at describing discipline and data-type specific requirements. Data have been collected among the seven early-adopter disciplines in the project, i.e. Climate Simulations, Earth & Environmental Sciences, Food Sciences, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, Linguistics, and Social Sciences. Recommendations, based on observed commonalities and needs, are structured around the Re-use Fitness model, presented in the EOSC EDEN Grant Agreement (2024).

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7 Appendix

Number	Title
7.1	Cannizzaro, G., & Smart, K. A. (2025). T3.1_DBM_Documents_V1, V1. <i>Zenodo</i> . https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15782232
7.2	Cannizzaro, G., Smart, K. A., & Lindlar, M. (2025). T3.1_DBM_Requirements_V1, V1. <i>Zenodo</i> . https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775751
7.3	Smart, K. A., Huber, R., Høier, S., Klemetsen, T., Mendes de Farias, T., & Cannizzaro, G. (2025). T3.1_DBM_Synthesized_Requirements_V1, V1. <i>Zenodo</i> . https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15782279
7.4	T3.1_Interviews_Informed_consent_V1
7.5	T3.1_Interview_guide_V1
7.6	T3.1_Management_Interviews_2025
7.7	Andreassen, H. N., Ciesla, M., Klemetsen, T., Parkes, O., & Sima, A.-C. (2025). T3.1_Interviews_Synthesized_Requirements_V1, V1. <i>Zenodo</i> . https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15782308
7.8	T3.1_FORD_classification_redistribution
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Informed Consent

Project: EOSC EDEN

Task 3.1 Definition of discipline-specific requirements and needs

You are invited to participate in an interview to contribute to enhancing strategies for digital preservation of digital objects (research data, software, etc.) as part of the EOSC EDEN project. Before your participation, please read the following information carefully to understand the purpose of the study and what your participation involves.

PROJECT STATEMENT

- As part of our project collaboration, we would like to inform you that the data collected and results generated during this study will be processed and shared between the two sister projects, EOSC EDEN (Grant Agreement nr 10118801) and FIDELIS (Grant Agreement nr 1011880).
- This study will be managed in line with the privacy notice shared between the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects (privacy policy [here](#)). All data gathered will be used for the project and study purposes. Anonymized data or results may also be utilized for future relevant Open Science initiatives.

STUDY STATEMENT

- The purpose of this study is to identify practices, recommendations, gaps and needs in scientific communities with regard to preservation of digital objects (research data, software, etc.). The study targets holders of research positions (levels R2-R4) and experienced research data repository personnel.
- Personal interviews will be audio-recorded by the means of equipment protecting the audio file, lasting approximately 60 minutes. Permission for recording will be sought from the participant beforehand. Any recording will be de-identified and transcribed, and retained securely during the project period. The recording will be deleted by the end of the project (2027-12-31).
- For the interview conducted under T3.1, ethical approval has been granted by Sikt – Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research.
- We process your information for research purposes in the public interest.

PARTICIPATION:

- Your participation in this study is voluntary.
- You have the right to object, access, rectification, erasure, restriction of processing and data portability.
- If you choose to discontinue your participation, you may withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without this entailing any penalty or negative consequences.
- If you withdraw from this project after completing the study, the original files containing your data may be destroyed at your request where feasible. However, the study results circulated via online or offline means may remain available, making your consent practically irrevocable once given.

RISKS:

- No risks are foreseen from this study. Any information likely to be damaging to your reputation will not be reported. The text of any attributed quote will be made available to you for approval before its initial publication. You will not be asked any questions about sensitive or personal topics.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

- All data collected in this project will be stored securely in a protected cloud service at UiT The Arctic University of Norway, and they will only be accessible to the project partners of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS during the project period. Your responses will be anonymized before publishing, meaning that your name and any other identifying information will at no point be linked to your answers. If you have any concerns about this, please contact us at privacy.edenfidelis@postit.csc.fi before proceeding.
- By the end of the project, data that can be archived will be archived, either openly or with suitable access restriction, in data repositories approved by the data controllers (UiT The Arctic University of Norway and CSC - IT Center for Science).

AUDIO, VIDEO AND IMAGES:

- Only the interviewer and the assigned representatives will have access to the original digital files collected during this process.
- Edited and anonymised versions of text and material from this interview may be used in instruction, public talks, and other publications related to the project.

DISSEMINATION:

- By participating, you consent to the use of the anonymized data collected during this study along with the findings generated, which will be used for project purposes, including online and offline presentations and publications.
- By participating, you consent to the use of findings generated from the data will be published on the joint website of the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects when available and may also be posted to project social media channels (i.e., LinkedIn and BlueSky).
- By participating, you consent to the archiving of an anonymised version of your data in a data repository approved by the data controller.
- You may be contacted for permission to use the audio in online and offline presentations.

CONTACT:

- If you have any questions or concerns about the project or privacy issues, or if you wish to file a complaint, please contact our project ethical group at privacy.edenfidelis@postit.csc.fi. You may also contact the UiT Data Protection Officer at personvernombud@uit.no.
- For inquiries specifically related to the study content, you may reach out to the data collector at helene.n.andreassen@uit.no (Task leader, T3.1).

Please go to next page for signature

First name and last name (block letters):

E-mail address:

I have read and understood the information in this document, and I have received an answer to all my questions regarding this research. I give my consent to have an anonymised version of my data archived in a data repository approved by the data controller.

Date, signature

T3.1 Interview guide

1. Setting the context for the interview

1.1 Researcher Context

These interviews are intended to complement a survey and ongoing (WP1) work on EOSC EDEN to define core processes for active long term preservation, measures for quality assessment and processes for the reappraisal of digital objects' data and metadata over time. This work (T3.1) and associated desk research looks to consider how these key topics covered by EOSC EDEN are influenced by disciplinary and other specialist researcher and repository factors.

Other interviews undertaken with repository personnel will look in more detail at deposit, curation and preservation of digital objects' data and metadata. In our interviews with researchers we are particularly interested in the selection of repositories, the deposit process, and resource discovery, access and reuse from the perspective of your research discipline and speciality. What information do you need about a repository to select it as a place of deposit for your research outputs (any kind of digital objects) and what is your experience of requirements at the point of deposit in terms of requirements for metadata (including ontologies) and file formats.

From the point of view of a researcher seeking to reuse deposited digital objects from repositories we are interested in the disciplinary or other specialist needs you have for particular technologies, file formats, ontologies and other descriptive/semantic information. Does what the repository provides meet your current needs and how do you perceive your needs changing over time? Beyond 'technical compliance' do the digital objects you obtain from repositories meet your expectations for research quality and fitness for use? How do, or how could, repositories consult with you to ensure your technical, semantic and quality expectations?

Finally, we want to hear the researcher's perspective on what impacts the quality, value and usability of digital objects over time. What steps should repositories take to ensure they continue to provide data that meets your needs and what should influence repository decisions to stop preserving, or even providing basic access to digital objects in your discipline or speciality?

We understand that this is a broad and complex range of issues. The interviews will be of an open format, seeking to identify topics and issues at the disciplinary/specialist level that can be incorporated into future work. We're interested in where interviewees see opportunities and challenges, particularly areas which depend on intervention by humans with specific expertise, and where there is the potential for increased machine-actionability and automation. Anything that arises from researchers' needs for a repository to keep data and metadata accessible and usable for the long term (potentially indefinitely) is of particular relevance to EOSC EDEN.

1.2 Repository Context

These interviews are intended to complement a survey and ongoing (WP1) work on EOSC EDEN to define core processes for active long term preservation, measures for quality assessment and processes for the reappraisal of digital objects' data and metadata over time. This work (T3.1) and associated desk research looks to consider how these key topics covered by EDEN are influenced by disciplinary and other specialist repository factors.

For technical compliance issues we would expect that disciplines have more specific and potentially complex requirements for metadata schemas, file formats, specialist ontologies and different types of data to support discovery, access and reuse of digital objects. These factors may apply in different ways to requirements for compliance at the point of deposit (e.g. essential metadata or restricted file formats), steps to be taken by the repository during initial curation (e.g. enrichment of metadata or conversion to in-demand (= from users) formats for access and reuse), and for active preservation to ensure objects remain accessible and usable for the long term (e.g. use of low risk, non-proprietary formats and measures to update metadata, formats and ontologies over time). We are interested to understand how you engage with your community of users to identify their changing needs over time (community watch) and how this interacts with work to ensure that current and in-demand technologies (and associated formats) are used (technology watch), how your discipline/speciality approaches the reappraisal of digital objects over time (to make decisions about their value, retention and level of care required) and how this incorporates assessment of scientific quality (fitness for use).

We understand that this is a broad and complex range of issues for repositories. The interviews will be of an open format, seeking to identify topics and issues at the disciplinary/specialist level that can be incorporated into future work. We're interested in where interviewees see opportunities and challenges, particularly areas which depend on intervention by humans with specific expertise, and where there is the potential for increased machine-actionability and automation. Anything that arises from the repository mission to keep digital objects' data and metadata accessible and usable for the long term (potentially indefinitely) is of particular relevance to EDEN.

2. Interview questions

2.1 Researchers

2.1.1 Starting question/"ice breaker"

What are the main topics of your research? Which type of data do you typically work with, and how do you typically work with it (discovery/re-use, collection, handling, processing, archiving, sharing)?

2.1.2 The incentives for data deposit

- Is it often mandatory for you to deposit data (e.g. required by employer, funder)? If not, what motivates you to deposit data? [! keep in mind that people who are required to deposit also may have strong motivations for doing so, and they should have the chance to talk about these.]]
 - More detailed questions, if needed: Do you see any direct benefits for you as a researcher, for the scientific community and/or for society at large? Any (shifting or emerging) requirements, norms or practices in the community? Any external drivers (journals, institutions, funders)?

2.1.3 Long-term preservation of data

- What are the different production stages involved in data creation (e.g., discovering existing data, collecting and capturing raw data, processing, cleaning, organizing data, finalizing, archiving, publishing and derivative creation, etc.)? What is the input and output of each step, in terms of data/content type and file format?
- What influences your decision about which file formats to use (at the different stages? (pre-deposit: might be a conscious choice, pure norm in community; deposit: any regular requirements from repository or acquired knowledge about best practices?)
- How do you proceed in determining what to deposit?
- After deposit (with open or controlled access), how long should your data be kept available?
- Could your data be replaced or reproduced in the future? Do they (or do you consider them to) have an expiration date? If yes, can you explain why?

2.1.4 Interaction with repositories

- Could you elaborate on your experience with using repositories for deposit of your research output (data, software, ...)? Any positive or challenging aspects to highlight (any learning curve when it comes to FAIRness of own data)? Any aspects directly related to discipline-specific and/or data-type needs (e.g. requirements for metadata incl ontologies and file formats)?
 - If you have experience with multiple repositories, how would you compare them?

- If you were to deposit new research output (data, software, ...), which information would you need about a repository in order to select it for deposit? And which services would you expect/require from the repository?
 - (to prepare the interviewer, some possible answers could be:
 - Information you would need/that could be decisive: commitment to long-term preservation (= keep the data FAIR over time), discipline specific needs covered, all necessary/no unnecessary metadata, interoperability support/integrations with other systems, the repository is suggested/required by the journal, visibility in search engines, precise information, possible data citing,
 - Services to expect/require: fast responses, systemic help, guidance on FAIRification
- Given your experience working with your data type, do you see any aspects where you would need support from the repository during preparation and deposit of data? Do you have access to the required support? Where do you get support from?
- In light of your experience with working with your type of data, which repository practices bring added value or, conversely, make it difficult reusing them?
 - Any aspects that are particularly important for long-term preservation of datasets in your discipline?

2.1.5 The purpose of data deposit in trustworthy repositories

- If you were asked by your institution, funder or journal to select a trustworthy/trusted repository for your data, what would this be to you?

2.1.6 Reuse of data: Knowledge, norms & attitudes

- In which situations have you/do you search for and use existing data (instead of/in addition to producing your own)?
- a) Follow-up, if experience with search and reuse:
 - What are your experiences (positive or negative) to find data?
 - What are your experiences (positive or negative) to re-use data?
 - Have you had problems accessing and managing specific data types or file formats?
 - If yes: Can you further explain the situation? (it may depend on the researcher: software, equipment; or it may be a technical issue with the repository)
- b) Follow-up, if no experience with search and reuse:
 - Any particular reason why you haven't searched and/or used existing data?
 - Would you consider doing it? If not, why? (bear in mind that some could say yes it's useful but I would never do it because ...)
- What is/would be necessary for you to evaluate a dataset as trustworthy (and viable for reuse)?
 - Suggestions, if more details needed: That the data/material ...

- are from someone I know personally
 - are from someone I DO NOT know personally but who has a good reputation
 - are from someone at an institution with a good reputation
 - are from a (data) repository with a good reputation
 - comply with guidelines around collection and/or formatting
 - have good documentation and/or metadata
 - are certified or accredited by a third party
 - are commonly used by others
 - have been cited in a written publication (i.e. scientific journal article, book chapter, etc.)
 - have been peer reviewed?
 - are relatively new?
- In your opinion, what could be done to increase findability and reusability of data within your discipline?

2.1.7 [bonus question, if time permits]

There is an increasing focus on making research outputs available in trustworthy repositories, and we have already touched upon *incentives* for data depositing. Taking one step back before we end the interview; Any thoughts about how deposit and reuse of data and related material could contribute to the progress of science?

2.1.8 End of interview

Thank you for the interview. We are done with the official part now. Is there something you would like to add which was not addressed in the interview yet?

2.2 Repositories

2.2.1 Starting question/ "Ice breaker"

(Let them appraise what is important in their work context).

- What is the main focus of your repository? Who are your main user groups? What discipline(s) are represented? What kind of data do you typically preserve in the repository?

2.2.2 Long-term preservation policy

(Focusing especially on the appraisal and reappraisal practices)

- What are the strategies and policies for long-term preservation in your repository?

- Do you have different policies for collecting and preserving data from different stages of the research process - raw vs. processed vs. end-user data?
- Are there challenges with maintaining the level of data quality for long-term preservation in the repository (content quality, technical quality, metadata quality)?
- Are there challenges with maintaining the level of service quality for long-term preservation and access (securing access, data integrity, securing against attacks, system downtime etc.)?
- What are the appraisal and reappraisal practices in the repository?
- If relevant (= if they operate with retention periods, have assets for which retention is applicable), what procedures do you employ at the end of the retention period (deletion, deindexing, transfer to another repository, etc.)?

2.2.3 Governance & resources

How is the repository governed? Would you say it is challenging to achieve sustainability for this repository? Do you operate with a succession plan (for instance in case there is no further funding, shortage of competent staff, possible end of life server system or for x or y reason)?

2.2.4 Community watch

- How do you engage with your community of users to identify their changing needs for long-term preservation over time? How do your community of users and relevant discipline(s) approach the reappraisal of digital objects over time (to make decisions about their value, retention and level of care required)? What role does scientific quality (fitness for use) play in the reappraisal of digital objects over time in your repository?

What kind of tools are used when working with depositors (like user guides, personal guidance, user surveys or other ways of gathering information from the user community)?

2.2.5 Technology watch

- How do you work to ensure that current and in-demand technologies (and associated formats) are used within your long-term preservation?

- ("in-demand" = Demanded by the users for access and reuse, which depends on understanding user needs. In contrast to preservation formats, which a repository might be able to select without reference to the users.)
- What standards are important for your repository when cooperating with other repositories, registries or other systems on long-term preservation? What can be an important hindrance for cooperation around long-term preservation today, in your opinion? (can be connected to shared use of standards, existing interoperability, future plans or needs, theoretical vs practical obstacles etc).

2.2.6 End of interview

Thank you for the interview. We are done with the official part now. Is there something you would like to add which was not mentioned in the interview yet?

Open follow-up questions:

Could you explain what you mean by XY?

Could you give me an example of XY?

Could you walk me through what happened?

How did you respond to that situation?

How did you come to that conclusion/decision?

What factors influenced your decision?

Is there anything else you would like to add about that?

T3.1 Management interviews 2025							
A: Overview interviews							
Researcher 1							
Discipline	Partner	Date for interview	Interviewer	Code	Text file (name)	Transcript verification	Comments
Climate Simulations	DKRZ	2025-05-06	Anna-Lena Flügel	01res1w	Interview_01res1w_cleaned.txt	Malwina Ciesla	
Earth & Environmental Sciences	U Bremen	2025-05-15	Robert Huber	02res1d	Interview_02res1d_cleaned.txt	Terje Klemetsen	
Food Sciences	Premotec	2025-05-07	Karl Presser/Malwina Ciesla	03res1m	Interview_03res1m_cleaned.txt	Malwina Ciesla	
High-Energy Physics	CERN	2025-05-05	Wesley Middelbos	04res1l	Interview_04res1l_cleaned.txt	Terje Klemetsen	
Life Sciences & Bioinformatics	SIB	2025-05-06	Florence Mehl	05res1b	Interview_05res1b_cleaned.txt	Terje Klemetsen	
Linguistics	UiT	2025-05-05	Helene N. Andreassen	06res1f	Interview_06res1f_cleaned.txt	Helene N. Andreassen	
Social Sciences	UKDS	2025-05-15	Oliver Parkes	07res1k	Interview_07res1k_cleaned.txt	Helene N. Andreassen	
Researcher 2 (if time/available)							
Discipline	Partner			Code	Text file (name)	Transcript verification	Comments
Climate Simulations	DKRZ						
Earth and environmental sciences	U Bremen						
Food Sciences	Premotec						
High-Energy Physics	CERN						
Life Sciences & Bioinformatics	SIB	2025-05-07	Tarcisio Mendes de Farias	05res1z	Interview_05res1z_cleaned.txt	Terje Klemetsen	
Linguistics	UiT	2025-05-08	Helene N. Andreassen	06res1l	Interview_06res1l_cleaned.txt	Helene N. Andreassen	
Social Sciences	UKDS						
Repository manager 1							
Discipline	Partner			Code	Text file (name)	Transcript verification	Comments
Climate Simulations	DKRZ	2025-05-09	Andrea Lammert	01rep1h	Interview_01rep1h_cleaned.txt	Malwina Ciesla	
Earth & Environmental Sciences	U Bremen	2025-05-22	Robert Huber	02rep1s	Interview_02res1d_cleaned.txt	Terje Klemetsen	
Food Sciences	Premotec	2025-05-09	Malwina Ciesla	03rep1p	Interview_03rep1p_summary.docx	Malwina Ciesla	No sound file; to be converted to .txt
High-Energy Physics	CERN	2025-05-06	Wesley Middelbos	04rep1t	Interview_04rep1t_cleaned.txt	Terje Klemetsen	
Life Sciences & Bioinformatics	SIB	2025-05-13	Ana-Claudia Sima	05rep1b	Interview_05rep1b_cleaned.docx	Ana-Claudia Sima	Text to be converted to .txt
Linguistics	UiT	2025-05-07	Helene N. Andreassen	06rep1k	Interview_06rep1k_cleaned.txt	Helene N. Andreassen	
Social Sciences	UKDS	2025-08-09	Oliver Parkes	07rep1m	Interview_07rep1m_cleaned.txt	Helene N. Andreassen	
Repository manager 2 (if time/available)							
Discipline	Partner			Code	Text file (name)	Transcript verification	Comments
Climate Simulations	DKRZ						
Earth & Environmental Sciences	U Bremen						
Food Sciences	Premotec						
High Energy Physics	CERN	2025-05-07	Wesley Middelbos	04rep1l	Interview_04rep1l_cleaned.txt	Terje Klemetsen	
Life Sciences & Bioinformatics	SIB	2025-05-13	Ana-Claudia Sima	05rep2b	Same file as 05rep1b	Ana-Claudia Sima	Joint interview
Linguistics	UiT	2025-05-09	Helene N. Andreassen	06rep1t	Interview_06rep1t_cleaned.txt	Helene N. Andreassen	
Social Sciences	UKDS						
B: Respondent coding system							
Climate Simulations	zero1						

Earth & Environmental Sciences	zero2						
Food Sciences	zero3						
High Energy Physics	zero4						
Life Sciences & Bioinformatics	zero5						
Linguistics	zero6						
Social Sciences	zero7						
Researcher	res						
Repository personnel	rep						
Intials	1+personal initial						
	2+personal initial*						

*If more than 1 person per category with the same personal initial

C: Transcription conventions

What	How	Example					
uncertainty	[??WORD] or [??XXX]	[??National bank] ... (06res1f) ; [??XXX] (06res1l)					
name	[code]	Instead of "[person's name]": "I think he was getting exasperated like, [06res1f], this is not a big deal." (06res1f)					
home institution	[institution]	Instead of "Institutions's name": I think [institution] itself has chosen to focus mostly on open publishing (06res1f)					
citations	"..."	So having someone who's worked a lot with data saying, "OK, yeah, this is fine. But generally, this might be better." (06res1f)					
unnecessary repetitions	remove	Remove one of the "we're" here: "Yeah it's a good idea yeah exactly so we're we're collecting this " (03res1m)					
punctuation	add if necessary to not misunderstand completely, but do not spend very much time on this						

names	often necessary to correct	the system does not recognize all names (letters, upper vs. lower case), so these often need to be corrected. One example is Zenodo, which in one file was transcribed as "the nodo"					
Other instructions:							
Requirement: to add in beginning of line when new person starts talking:	I:	Interviewer (use I1 and I2 if there are two interviewers)					
	respondent code:	respondent, e.g. 03res1m					
Requirement (for readability):	make a line space before a new person starts talking						
Advice:	use a sound player that allows you to zoom in (useful if you need to go back). Helene uses Audacity.						

Fields of research and development

(FORD)

Table copied from page 59 in OECD. (2015). *Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>

Table 2.2. Fields of R&D classification

Broad classification	Second-level classification
1. Natural sciences	1.1 Mathematics 1.2 Computer and information sciences 1.3 Physical sciences 1.4 Chemical sciences 1.5 Earth and related environmental sciences 1.6 Biological sciences 1.7 Other natural sciences
2. Engineering and technology	2.1 Civil engineering 2.2 Electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering 2.3 Mechanical engineering 2.4 Chemical engineering 2.5 Materials engineering 2.6 Medical engineering 2.7 Environmental engineering 2.8 Environmental biotechnology 2.9 Industrial biotechnology 2.10 Nano-technology 2.11 Other engineering and technologies
3. Medical and health sciences	3.1 Basic medicine 3.2 Clinical medicine 3.3 Health sciences 3.4 Medical biotechnology 3.5 Other medical science
4. Agricultural and veterinary sciences	4.1 Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries 4.2 Animal and dairy science 4.3 Veterinary science 4.4 Agricultural biotechnology 4.5 Other agricultural sciences
5. Social sciences	5.1 Psychology and cognitive sciences 5.2 Economics and business 5.3 Education 5.4 Sociology 5.5 Law 5.6 Political science 5.7 Social and economic geography 5.8 Media and communications 5.9 Other social sciences
6. Humanities and the arts	6.1 History and archaeology 6.2 Languages and literature 6.3 Philosophy, ethics and religion 6.4 Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music) 6.5 Other humanities